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TO THE PROBLEM OF CRITICISM OF EURYTHMY AS A SCIENTIFICALLY UNFOUNDED METHOD IN PEDAGOGY

Zahraa Al Shehab

Second-Year Master's Student of the
State Academy of Choreography Uzbekistan

Annotation

The article is devoted to the analysis of criticism of eurythmy as a therapeutic and pedagogical method of psycho-emotional development of a personality. Exploring the scientific literature on this issue, the author comes to the conclusion about the insufficient development of the categorical-conceptual apparatus and eurythmy as a kind of pedagogical and therapeutic activity, as a component of **Waldorf pedagogy**. At the same time, relying on his pedagogical experience, as well as the results of official research, the author proves that the lack of scientific reliability in itself should not be considered as evidence of the complete inefficiency of the method.

On the contrary, such insufficiency should be considered as an incentive for additional research that allows to «filter» the existing categorical-conceptual apparatus from «metaphysical concepts», to clarify the theoretical and methodological foundations of the process in order to more effectively adapt it to solving general and particular psychotherapeutic and pedagogical tasks of an individual.

Keywords and phrases: eurythmy, Waldorf pedagogy, scientific reliability, method effectiveness.

Introduction

The relevance of the topic of this article is defined by the permanent increase in the requirements for the quality and effectiveness of the amount of methods that are applied to the individual in the course of one's education, socialization education at the present stage. We are talking about a very large conglomerate of technologies, methods, specific techniques and exercises for psychophysical development and health protection. Due to the specifics of the organization of thinking in developed and developing societies, one of the most important criteria for the admissibility and effectiveness of a particular method is the scientific validity of its content and the reliability of the results of its application.

The fact of insufficient scientific substantiation and reliability can, in particular cases, become in public perception similar to a "stigma", at least indicating the futility of the practice under study, at the maximum, making it perceived as a fraud.

In this regard, eurythmy – the art of the artistic movement, as one of the most important parts of Waldorf pedagogy, but also used more and more often in educational practices that are not related to this system, is regularly criticized as a kind

of activity that should contribute to a harmonious psychophysical (intellectual, emotional, physical, etc.) personal development.

It would be more correct to say that such criticism falls not only on eurythmy, but on the entire Waldorf pedagogy, which is often perceived as a kind of theosophy and anthroposophy - philosophical doctrines, axiomatics of which, in the most appropriate expression, is extremely different from the axiomatics of modern science. Accordingly, the contradiction between real pedagogical practice, in which the popularity of eurythmy is constantly growing in Europe, the USA and Russia, and the attitude towards it from the scientific community determines the purpose of this article - to explain this contradiction and determine the ways in which criticism of eurythmy would not become a way of its denial, but its improvement.

First of all, it is necessary to define the concept of "eurythmy". According to the definition of B.M. Bim-Bad, it should be understood as "the art of movements developed in the first third of the XX century on the basis of the anthroposophy of R. Steiner. It gives a visible figurative form to the sound of speech and music and can act in combination with other arts (for example, in M.A. Chekhov's "Technique of the Actor")" [3, p. 322].

The term itself is of Greek origin. In the era of Antiquity, they called it the quality of an object, which later started to be denoted by another word - "harmony". In other words, eurythmy was understood as the proportionality and orderliness of the elements. At the beginning of the XX century, the creator of Waldorf pedagogy, a philosopher who practiced occultism, a mystic, but at the same time a very extraordinary teacher, Rudolf Steiner started defining the word as the type of activity he created for the psycho-emotional and physical development of children, which was a synthesis of poetic word, movement, light and music. In other words, we are talking about a syncretic type of activity. However, R. Steiner himself called this activity as the art or a type of creativity. «The question is - what is actually depicted in this case? You will understand what is depicted in eurythmy only when you consider that eurythmy wants to be a visible language. This is the case, after all, with speech itself: when we express speech mimetically, we take ordinary speech as a model, but when we express speech itself, then it has no model. The person reflects it as an independent work. There is nowhere in nature what is revealed in speech - is revealed by it. In the same way, eurythmy should be something that represents some kind of primary creativity" [6, p. 6].

Indeed, syncretism is one of the most important features of primitive kinds of activity, which can be attributed to proto-art, a kind of "primary creativity." However, for this type of activity, the matter of almost paradoxical combinations of extremely rigid regulation of action and improvisation are quite possible and characteristic. Actually, a similar combination can be found in eurythmy. There are well-defined standards of movements (for example, round dances, and various other fixed positions of dance

participants, accompanied by various speech sounds and music) in this so called "art", but at the same time, eurythmy is impossible without improvisation, and is, indeed, composed for almost any text.

«There is a frequent usage practice of poetic rhythms (iambic, trochee, anapaest, dactyl, etc.) to poems by various poets during "eurythmy classes". Rhythms are played in motion through a step, or accompanied by hand gestures. There is also a possibility of using balls or sticks. The exercises are performed both individually and jointly with other participants. An important aspect is the interaction of arms and legs, which develops coordination of movements. Using various rhythms, one can have a calming or activating effect» writes M.A. Grachev [4, p. 134].

Eurythmy, according to R. Steiner, is the possibility of connecting **body, soul and mind** - into a harmonious unity triad.

The use of syncretic artistic activity in teaching aimed at the creative development of the child is a widespread practice. Indeed, the teaching of folk art to children of preschool and primary school age, which is so popular in the countries of the post-Soviet space, represents an introduction to the type of syncretic activity. Its great advantage in the context of the goals and objectives of the educational process is the complexity of the impact, the formation of a very wide range of sensorimotor skills implemented using different modes of thinking in complex coordination.

In the modern categorical and conceptual apparatus of pedagogy, there are no statements about the need to develop the triad (mind, soul, body) as a whole, however, when it comes to the theoretical justifications for teaching children folk art, in particular, the art of dance, one can find statements that such a practice contributes to the harmonious development of psycho-emotional, physical and communicative personalities.

But it is eurythmy that incurs extremely strong criticism from the scientific community, and also from the ones considering themselves to be in support of the scientific community, as well as the notorious "traditional values" of segments of society. D. Dugan in his "Skeptical Encyclopedia of Pseudoscience" considered eurythmy practically as a ritual act, as a quasi-religious practice, certainly affecting the psycho-emotional sphere of the personality, but hardly having a confirmed health-saving effect [7, p. 31]

An attempt to create a holistic faculty, in which, as a scientific discipline, the anthroposophical direction of healing approach developed by R. Steiner at the University of Aberdeen (Scotland) in 2012 led to a grandiose scandal. Many prominent representatives of the scientific community called it incomprehensible that at present, practices based on mystical thinking can be developed and learned in a scientific institution as equal to other scientific disciplines [9].

In the countries of the post-Soviet space, the part of society which is close to conservative religious cults, in particular, to the Russian Orthodox Church, are

especially active in actions: «Steiner's teaching itself is a syncretic combination of Western and Eastern religious and occult teachings, in which elements of Gnosticism, Pythagorean mysticism of numbers can be distinguished, Kabbalistics, occultly interpreted Christianity ... A whole system of initiation levels was developed with initiation rites like Masonic ones. The first steps included dancing, development of eurythmy, as well as, staging theatrical mysteries. Special secret courses were read for the initiates. A person, according to the teachings of Steiner, in accordance with the traditions of ancient occultism, forms a microcosm in the composition of the physical, etheric and astral bodies, and the etheric body descends into a person with the eruption of molars (about 6 years), and the rest - with the achievement of puberty ... Attempts separating the methods of the Waldorf schools from their occult soil ... are clearly meaningless. Russia is the country in which even non-religious phenomena acquire a religious meaning - this is the way the famous Russian priest, deacon Andrey Kuraev defines Waldorf pedagogy and, in particular, eurythmy [8].

On the perspective of conservative religious organizations, such "attacks" seem quite understandable. There is also a competition for the right of ideological influence, and the fact of how young and pioneer the eurythmy actually is - should not be forgotten. Conservative social institutions simply have not had time to get used to it yet. After all, the Russian Orthodox Church does not subject the same sharp criticism to the practice of teaching Russian folk art to children in schools, which in the conditions of modern society has turned out to be completely separable from its pagan soil.

The criticism of eurythmy and Waldorf pedagogy by the scientific community has to be drawn of more attention. In the process of preparing this article, we were unable to find critical judgments that would be aimed at criticizing the practices themselves. In the overwhelming majority of cases, there is a talk about a theoretical and methodological justification about mystical thinking that is completely unacceptable for science, which resulted in the emergence of these practices.

When it comes to analysis of aforementioned practices without referencing them to occult ideologemes - their assessment, in particular, the assessment of eurythmy, as a rule, is positive. M.A. Gracheva, whose quotation from the article "The Art of the Eurythmic Movement as an Element of Healing in the Educational Process" was given above proves the viability of this type of activity in great detail and convincingly as developing the child's psycho-emotional sphere, communication skills (in particular, teamwork skills) and ultimately having a healing effect: "Eurythmic movements help the child in self-expression. Children learn to show their own individuality through art on the basis of an artistic image and they understand that each person is unique ... Breath training is also an obligatory and important element of eurythmic exercises. But this is not only about inhalation or exhalation through the lungs (although this aspect can gradually improve too), but about two polar movements expressed in us,

such as contraction and expansion, concentration and relaxation, heaviness and lightness, isolation and a feeling of straightness. etc." [4, p. 134].

E.D. Piradova, in her study on eurythmy as an educational practice, points out that «The formation of a eurythmy gesture as a projection, as a process and result of understanding and generating meanings, consists in the conscious development of the so-called compound states that have arisen, for example, on the basis of a musical or literary work and their visualization which, under the influence of its own semantic forms (symbolic forms) with pronounced new signs of synesthesia, affects the viewer with its specific means of expression" [5, p. 17].

The abovementioned judgments are largely proved by the pedagogical activity of the author of this article. The work that she has been implementing for several years now with children of different age categories, including children with disabilities of various types, gives grounds for conducting in the foreseeable future a full-fledged, with a claim to complete reproducibility, experimental research in which eurythmy practices would become independent variable, while children's communication skills, as well as their objectively measured parameters of their creative imagination and emotional sphere, are the dependent variable.

The problem is that from the author's point of view, many useful practices, as the historical process convincingly demonstrates us, do not immediately receive a comprehensive and consistent theoretical and methodological basis. For example, the healing effect of music has been known since the ancient times. However, in spite of the fact that a wide range of mechanisms of perception and psycho-emotional response to musical narration was discovered only in modern times, this did not prevent the use of music to correct the psychophysical state of a person either in Antiquity, or in the Middle Ages, or in modern times.

Such a collision can be formulated as follows: what works well does not always need to have an explanation.

Summing up all of the above, we note that scientific knowledge, among other mental systems for mastering reality, differs, perhaps, by the most effective "fuse" from turning into a set of ideologemes that are not subject to the critical analysis - epistemology. At the same time, the reliability of epistemology does not mean that it is ideal – this would simply contradict the very essence of scientific knowledge. And the risk of turning knowledge into dogma remains even in the case of science. The risk arises, among other things, under the influence of various directions in the value judgments of public opinion, due to which the phenomenon and its description often is not particularly differentiated.

It seems quite obvious that from the standpoint of strict scientific knowledge, the categorical-conceptual apparatus of eurythmy does not withstand absolutely any criticism. Filled with concepts from metaphysical (sometimes even occult) teachings, it is something like a "red canvas" for the "angry bull" of public opinion, or rather that

part of it that is superficially familiar with only a limited number of criteria for scientific judgment, unconsciously turning them into dogmatics. However, with a high degree of probability, based on all of the abovementioned theories, it can be assumed, that while developing eurythmy, R. Steiner as a result created something that works effectively, but at the same time was described not in scientific categories, but in categories close to the worldview paradigm of its creator. And in this case, the main attention of the science of pedagogy in this segment of educational technologies should be focused, first of all, on identifying, confirming (or refuting) the effectiveness of eurythmy practices themselves, outside the description, the rationale that is offered to it by the apologists of Waldorf pedagogy and theosophy. Focusing on the dynamics of the objective parameters of the student's personality, as well as, having one's body undergoing the influence of eurythmy is the true goal of the scientific study of this issue. And if the effectiveness of these practices as developing and health-saving educational technologies is confirmed by the number of experiments (which is justified by reasons), then the question of creating a new, scientific theory of eurythmy will eventually become relevant.

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THE ESSENCE OF ORGANIZING CHILDREN'S ACTIVITIES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Pulatova P. M.

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami, Faculty of Special
Pedagogy and Inclusive Education, Professor of the Department of
Oligophrenopedagogy, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences

Kultemirova G.

2nd Year Master Student

Annotation

The article emphasizes the importance of the child's participation in various activities in the formation of the personality of preschoolers, the further development of all types of vigorous activity, the formation of valuable spiritual qualities in children: patience is satisfaction, independence, organization, the formation of a community is one of the main important tasks in the education of preschool children.

Introduction

One of the main factors of socio-economic development in the world is the development of the intellectual potential of the individual on the basis of modern requirements, raising it to a new qualitative level. The concept of international education, defined by international organizations and most countries of the world until 2030, states that "a solid foundation of knowledge, the development of creative thinking" is an urgent task, which, in turn, creates the need to develop the intellectual potential of children in preschool education based on pedagogical support in cooperation with UNESCO. Pedagogical support for pupils of preschool educational institutions is considered as a key factor in intellectual development. This requires the development of professional competencies, updating the content of education, such as the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of preschool education in 2017-2021" DP-2727 and other regulatory documents to prepare children for schooling.

Participation in various activities forms the personality of a preschooler. One of the main tasks of educating preschool children is the further improvement of all aspects of vigorous activity and the formation on this basis of valuable spiritual qualities: independence, organization, sociability. The tutor's guidance will be aimed at further enriching the content of the activity and methods of its implementation, the formation of the ability to jointly plan activities, cooperate in the process of activity, and achieve certain results with common aspirations. An indicator of the success of children's play activities, including creative play activities, are the following skills: reflection in games of positive events in social life, coordination of the game, joint definition of the plot, fair

distribution of roles, independent preparation of the play environment, active development. the plot, understanding each other in the game, reaching out, supporting friendly baskets, fully understanding its meaning, carrying toys and materials to the place without reminders. As a rule, especially in games common among seven-year-old children, the formation of gaming skills is manifested in the fact that children with intellectual disabilities are able to follow the rules of the game and establish friendly relations between the players.

In the labor activity of children with intellectual disabilities in preschool educational institutions, the educator uses them to form in them a sense of independence, diligence, patience, organization and responsibility. In the labor activity of children with intellectual disabilities in preschool educational institutions, the educator uses them to form in them a sense of independence, diligence, patience, organization and responsibility. When evaluating shifts, the educator relies on the opinion of the team: the quality of work is assessed, as well as the responsible attitude of the duty officers to their duties, the ability to fairly distribute tasks, work together, and adhere to cultural rules of conduct.

The content and organization of the collective work of children with intellectual disabilities in preschool organizations are complex. Children with intellectual disabilities work in groups, and work within a group is often done in the form of collaborative work. Students successfully master the basics of working in a team, children with intellectual disabilities, an indicator of independence and organization of work, understand the purpose of work (or are able to set it on their own), plan the stages of the labor process with a teacher-defectologist and present the results, allocate the necessary equipment and materials, distribute with the help of a teacher (or independently), the acquisition of basic labor skills and abilities in accordance with the "Preschool Education Program" The main professional skills and abilities are the ability to work together, be kind to each other and help each other, achieve positive results, correctly assess the quality of work. When an educator directs children, he requires children to be accurate in achieving results in work, dexterity and ingenuity in mastering materials and means of labor. In the working corner there should be everything necessary for independent work with types of work understandable to children. Children with intellectual disabilities develop a sense of responsibility for maintaining equipment, toys, aids, order in the group room.

The teacher conducts a wide program of physical education in large and preparatory groups: supports active movement in the group, improves all types of movements, engages in various sports with children, organizes sports activities and competitions, constantly monitors the posture of children. uses various hardening methods. Proper physical education is the key to active children's skills in school.

It is important to nurture an active interest and desire for school in children with intellectual disabilities. To solve this problem, a general direction of work has been determined to prepare children with intellectual disabilities for preschool education, as well as special work: school excursions, the work done in this way forms in children a serious desire to become a new, proud student by the end of preschool age.

Thus, the entire system of correctional work with children with intellectual disabilities should be aimed at a gradual restructuring of the psyche, behavior, activities and personality of preschool children, the formation of an active comprehensive preparation of children for the new conditions of school education. This will serve as a basis for faster admission of children with intellectual disabilities to school and increase the effectiveness of learning.

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ENHANCING STUDENTS' ORAL AND WRITTEN SPEECH THROUGH EDUCATIONAL DICTATIONS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL MOTHER TONGUE CLASSES

Ahmadjonova Mahfuza Egamkulovna,
Senior Lecturer, Department of Primary Education,
Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

Annotation

The article analyzes the methods of organizing educational dictations in the process of primary school mother tongue lessons. The theoretical foundations of educational dictation are scientifically illuminated.

Keywords: Elementary class, dictation, educational dictation, oral and written speech, knowledge, method, school

Introduction

One of the main goals of teaching mother tongue and literature in primary school is to improve children's speech and increase their literacy. The role of educational dictations in the further development of this work is enormous. Dictation in school relies heavily on children's auditory perception. Children's imagination also plays a decisive role in this. An important aspect of dictation is that it prepares children to write independently and correctly. With this in mind, each student should incorporate each rule interpreted from the spelling into the children's writing in different ways. In this area, too, dictation is a necessary way of working.

Dictation is derived from the Latin word *dikto* (dictation), which means to tell, to speak, to speak.

Dictation is not only a method of checking knowledge, but also a method of consolidating knowledge. The content of dictation has completely changed by our time: many types of dictation, emphatic, explanatory, visual, creative, free education have emerged, leaving only the name of the dictation, and the essence has become a kind of spelling exercises.

With the help of dictation, students are required to be able to apply orthographic, grammatical theoretical knowledge to writing in a short

period of time (in the process of dictation writing), which occurs depending on the mental activity of students. Students should be able to comprehend the spelling of the words they are writing while dictating, while at the same time being able to recall the theoretical knowledge learned and apply it in writing. Only then can students write without error. This requires thorough knowledge and automatic skills from students. Dictation in a variety of forms allows the teacher to work closely with the teacher while automatically teaching students to write words independently, without errors, correctly.

It is known that different forms of dictation help students to strengthen the theoretical knowledge of spelling, grammar, the ability to apply this theoretical knowledge in writing, to help students identify shortcomings in writing and the causes of its occurrence. Dictation also determines the extent to which students have mastered certain grammatical topics. This means that advanced teachers make effective use of dictation, bringing it deeper and deeper into life. Consolidation of spelling knowledge given to students can be tested by dictation of their knowledge on one or more topics. This means that through dictation we give students both spelling knowledge and test the given spelling knowledge.

Educational dictations serve to reinforce a spelling-grammatical theme in the child's mind and teach him to apply this theoretical knowledge in writing. Such dictations are conducted in the classroom with the active participation of the teacher and students: before dictation, students are reminded of one or more topics to be reinforced, the spelling of the necessary words is shown, and the teacher is allowed to write the words if students are sure that they are not misspelled. In some cases, during dictation, students are asked to ask the teacher to spell words whose spelling is unknown, and then, after writing or writing, the teacher is given the right to determine the spelling of the word and correct their mistake accordingly. Organizing the work in this way teaches students to write without mistakes. Increases their spelling sensitivity, prevents the erroneous form of words from becoming ingrained in the reader's memory. Educational dictations also have a test character. During the interview, the teacher will also have the opportunity to identify gaps in students'

knowledge, possible errors in writing, looking for measures to eliminate these shortcomings immediately.

Educational dictation is conducted by the teacher in different contexts and for different purposes: dictation can be recorded after a new topic has been covered. In this case, the teacher writes the spelling of each word that is unfamiliar to the children on the board, explains its spelling orally, and then reminds the students to write the word by asking some students to relate the spelling to the grammar topic they have just covered. This kind of dictation serves as an exercise that reinforces the new topic.

In the process of writing this form of dictation, students become accustomed to independently apply the theoretical knowledge they have acquired from grammar to writing, in which case they are forced to think independently, to make their own judgments about a spelling rule. This lays the groundwork for students to acquire conscious knowledge.

Sometimes, educational dictation can be used to reinforce a topic that has been inculcated in children in a variety of ways over the course of several previous lessons, as well as to identify gaps in students' knowledge and find ways to correct them. In doing so, the teacher encourages students to think more independently, to find their own mistakes, to apply the learned theoretical knowledge to writing without anyone's help.

It is also possible to link educational dictation to multiple topics. There is a special lesson for dictation, depending on the purpose of dictation.

Depending on the purpose of the teacher in the relevant lesson, different tasks are assigned to the educational dictation:

1. The teacher uses educational dictation in order to eliminate various spelling errors in students' writing. At the same time, the teacher pays attention to the thorough mastery of phonetic and grammatical knowledge and their incorporation into children's writing.
2. The aim is to theoretically inculcate certain spelling knowledge in the minds of children through dictation. Assignments can be given, such as extracting relevant words from the text and underlining one of the parts of speech. It is also important to note that even in this type of dictation, students' spelling errors are not left out of the teacher's focus.
3. Dictation is also used to enhance students' speech. At the same time, students take a serious approach to the text of dictation. Students are

required to complete tasks such as adding the necessary words or phrases to the text provided for writing. This kind of task not only activates words in students' speech, but also teaches them to think freely. Develops the ability to express one's opinion in writing

So, depending on the intended purpose, educational dictations are divided into three types:

1. Educational dictations of spelling character.
2. Educational dictations that strengthen theoretical knowledge.
3. Educational dictations of speech nature.

Educational dictations of orthographic character.

This type of educational dictation is used to prevent spelling errors. In this case, the spelling of words that are unfamiliar to the child is explained in a timely manner.

The teacher reminds students of the spelling of unfamiliar words in different ways: reminds them of the spelling rules learned in the previous lesson or in this lesson and links it to the writing, or reminds them of this rule, and children find examples of this, and so on.

This kind of dictation is a dictation of a purely educational nature intended to reinforce knowledge.

This means that in educational dictation of a spelling nature, at the request of the teacher, students become active participants in the lesson. The main goal of the lesson is based on the active thinking of students, their independent approach to the spelling of words in the text. The teacher consistently monitors the students' comments, thoughts, and opinions, and corrects them at the same time if he or she feels a little biased.

Based on the above, we interpret this type of educational dictation into the following types:

1. Emphasis dictation.
2. Explanatory dictation.
3. Explanatory dictation.
4. Conversation dictation.
5. Dictionary dictation.
6. Mixed dictation.
7. Hearing dictation.
8. Visual dictation.

The main task in the study of word groups is to develop students' oral and written speech, to enrich their vocabulary with new nouns, adjectives, numbers, verbs, to gain a clear understanding of the meaning of words used by students so far, to use appropriate words in related speech. In order to successfully solve these tasks, in the process of learning word groups, regular work is done on synonyms, antonyms (terms are not given), students are introduced to polysemous words, their use in their own and figurative sense. At the same time, it is important to link education with students' personal experiences, what they have seen, heard on the radio, and learned from books.

In addition to observing students, developing skills of perceiving important things, enriching their knowledge of the environment, the task of developing their speech is also performed.

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ANTHROPOTOPONYMS ARE A PRICELESS TREASURE OF OUR LANGUAGE, A MONUMENT OF OUR HISTORY

Nizomiddinova Dildora Nosirovna

Kokand DPI Department of Primary Education Great Teacher

Annotation

Anthropotoponyms are the product of different social periods and are one of the most historical toponymic layers in the vocabulary of a language. Such place names originated with the emergence of a society based on private property.

Keywords: Toponym, zoonym, onomastics, oykonim, ethnonym, anthroponym, anthropotoponym, anthroponecronym, anthropohydronym, anthroporonym, anthropooykonim.

Introduction

Anthroponymy and toponymy are historically inextricably linked. They both learn famous horses in the language. Anthroponymy deals with the study of human names, while toponymy deals with the study of place names. Names, nicknames, surnames of people included in the scope of anthroponyms, place names created on their basis are called anthropotoponyms.

Anthropotoponyms are the product of different social epochs and are one of the most historical toponymic layers in the vocabulary of languages. Such place names originated with the emergence of a society based on private property. Settlements - villages, mahallas, forts, auls, guzars, streets - began to be named after the authoritative people who founded, built and spent money on landscaping.

Anthropotoponyms have a special place in the system of place names of the republic, especially in the Fergana valley. A group of such anthropotoponyms originated during the Kokand Khanate. Most of them are named after khans and their children, brothers, cousins, officials who held important positions in the palace, clerics, clergy. Examples of place names based on the names of Kokand khans are Sheralichek in Balikchi district of Andijan region, Khudoyorkhan and Mallakhon in Uzbekistan district of Fergana region. These oykonims are directly connected with the names of Sheralikhan, who ruled the khanate in 1842-1845, Khudoyorkhan, who ruled the khanate for about 25 years, and Mallakhon, who ruled the khanate in 1858-1862. The villages of Chek Nasriddin in Rishtan district of Fergana region, Nasriddinabad in Balikchi district of Andijan region, and Ormonbek are named after Khudoyorkhan's sons Nasriddinbek and Ormonbek. Among the toponyms formed on the basis of the names of ancestors and relatives of the khans are the toponyms Hojibek guzari in Kokand, Hojibek in Besharik district, Sultanmuradbek in Balikchi district. Hojibek was the younger brother of Kokand khan Norbutakhan, who served as a khokim in the khanate's city of Uratapa

and Turakurgan. Sultanmurodbek - Khudoyorkhan's brother; he ruled the principality of Margilan from 1853 until the end of the khanate with some interruptions.

Some of the anthropotonyms in the Fergana Valley are based on the names of civil servants of the khanate period - high-ranking officials, high-ranking officials, military commanders. Examples of such toponyms are Muslimqulariq, Risqulibek guzari, Holmatdodho, Oftobachichek, Sheralimingboshi. Musulmonqulariq is located in Balikchi district of Andijan region. This name is directly related to the name of the Muslim, who played an important role in the socio-political and economic life of the Kokand khanate in the 40s and early 50s of the XIX century. In the Muslim khanate, he rose to the rank of prime minister. He dug a canal on the left bank of the Kara-Darya in the mid-19th century. The canal came to be known as the Muslim Valley after him.

The place called Risqulibek guzari in Kokand was named after the great military commander Irisqulibek. According to Ya. Dadaboev, a researcher at the city museum of local lore, based on historical sources, Irisqulibek Norbotabiy's wife was a half-brother (one father, one mother) and a cousin of the Kokand khans Olimkhan and Umarkhan. He began his military service in the army of Olimkhan as the head of the unit (the head of the unit carrying and guarding the flag of the military unit) and at the end of his life reached the highest military rank - commander. Irisqulibek showed examples of heroism in the battles fought to strengthen and centralize the khanate. At the same time, he has done a lot for the improvement and development of the neighborhood where he lives. He built a mosque, a school and a bazaar in the neighborhood. That is why the mahalla guzar was named Risqulibek guzar out of respect for him.

The village of Kholmatdodho is located in the Asaka district of Andijan region. The name of the place is derived from the name of a person named Kholmuhammad, who held one of the positions in the khanate - dodho. According to sources in the history of the Kokand khanate, most of the land in the Asaka region was owned by a senior official, Kholmuhammad dodho, the son of Muhammad Nazar Qushbegi. The village, which was built on the lands owned by Kholmuhammad Dodho, is named after him as above. In the list of settlements published in 1909 in Skobelev (now Fergana), the name of the village appears as Chek Holmat dodho.

Oftobachichek is the name of one of the settlements of Altynkul district of Andijan region. The village is named after Abdurahmon Oftobachi, the son of a Muslim, a historical figure who had a great reputation during the reigns of Sheralikhan and Khudoyorkhan, one of the Kokand khans. Abdurahman was appointed by Khudoyorkhan as an oftobachi, so the word oftobachi was used next to his name. Khudoyorkhan, taking into account the services of the sun, gave him a check of several hundred acres of land in the territory of Andijan. This place, which is expressed in historical documents in the form of the check of Abdurahman oftobach, has shrunk over time and taken the form of Oftobachichek.

Sherali, one of the streets in Kokand, is named after him. The settlement is named after the military commander Sherali, who left an indelible mark on the history of the Kokand Khanate and gained great prestige. Sherali was the commander of the cavalry during the reign of Kokand khan Khudoyorkhan, who showed heroism in the fight against the invaders. Historian, Professor R. Nabiev in his work "From the history of the Kokand Khanate" ("Iz istorii Kokandskogo khanstva") on the basis of historical sources of that period noted some information about the commander Sherali. It is said that he was a broad-shouldered, stocky man, a skilled horseman. He amazed everyone with his fearlessness, bravery and courage. 14 were wounded in battles with the enemy. He died heroically in a battle with General Skobelev's army.

In addition, in the territory of Uzbekistan district of Fergana region there are Dasturkhanchi, Kozikalon, Elchi, Ghaznachi in Buvayda district, Mirishkor in Uchkuprik district, Naib's bridge in Kokand, Devonbegi, Bakovul toponyms, which are added to personal names. In fact, the mentioned toponyms are Dastarkhanchi village - Mahmud Dastarkhanchi, Naib's bridge, Devonbegi, Bakovul streets - Otabek naib, Muhammad Razzoq devonbegi, Otab bakovul.

Among the place names there are anthropotonyms based on the names of religious figures. Examples are the toponyms Sheikhuslam Guzar and Khalifa Safa in Kokand. Shaykh al-Islam is the highest title in Muslim society, meaning the head of the clergy. The names of Sultankhan Tora Ahrori, Marufkhon Tora bin Mamurkhan Tora, Sulaymon Khoja bin Yusufkhan Khoja, Eshan Bobohoja Konibodomiy, Zokirkhoja Eshan Namangani, Khoja Kalon Joyboriy, who held the position of Sheikhuslam in the Kokand khanate, have been preserved in the sources. Of these, Zokirkhoja Eshan Namangani was honored to leave his name to Guzar. Guzar was originally called Shaykh al-Islam Zakirkhoja Eshan Guzar. Later it was simplified in pronunciation and was called Shaykh al-Islam guzari.

The name of Khalifa Safa mahalla in the city was based on the name of Khalifa Safa, a great religious figure of his time. According to sources, Khalifa Safa was a student of the famous Sheikh Khalifa Hussein Bukhari from Bukhara and was one of the famous Ishans. He had a large number of disciples from different strata of the population⁸. He taught at the Jame 'madrassa. He had a great reputation in Dorulsaltanat.

It should be noted that in the system of place names of the Fergana Valley there are many anthropotonyms formed from the combination of a person's name and the word check. The word check was included in toponyms meaning "private land". In fact, in the past, chek meant the private lands of khans and family members, officials, religious leaders, and other people in general. Ahmadkhochek of Shahrikhan district of Andijan region, Farmonchek, Bobochek, Sariqmirzachek of Asaka district, Yusufkhalifa cheki, Usmoncheki, Turamcheki, Mallachek of Balikchi district, Niyozmatchek, Sottikhochek of Pakhtaabad district, Jumaykaban of Furinka district of Altynkul district, Izbashapchek of Uzbekistan, Such anthropotonyms include the

names of villages such as Chek Sharif in the district of Chek Sharif, Mahmudchek, Mirsultonchek, Mavlonchek, Ismailchek, Sherazimchek, Dustmatchek, Egamberdichek in the Naryn district of Namangan region.

A certain group of anthropotonyms emerged during the years of independence. Some of the mahallas, streets and parks of the cities and districts of the Republic are the great scholars of the East - Burhoniddin Marginoni, Ahmad Fergani, Termezi, Zamakhshari, Imam Bukhari, Bahauddin Naqshband, Khoja Ahror, Najmiddin Kubro, Rudaki, Alisher Navoi, Ali Kushchi; The great commanders who sacrificed their lives for the motherland - Spitamen, Muqanna, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, Temur Malik, Amir Temur.

So, anthropotonyms are the priceless treasure of our language, the monument of our ancient history, the echo of music. Thorough scientific study of them is important for linguistics, history, ethnography.

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THE STUDY OF PROJECTIVE METHODS IN PSYCHOLOGY

Hoshimova Dilorom Anvarovna

Teacher of the Department of Interfaculty Pedagogy and
Psychology of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

Annotation

This article is about the scientific and practical issues of personality psychology, and provides information on the level of study, convenience, capabilities, effectiveness of projective methods in psychology.

Keywords: Psychodiagnostics, projection, projective methods, personality, personality psychology, sublimation, rationalization, catharsis, need, motive, mental state and others.

Introduction

It is known that one of the important goals of the education policy pursued in our country is to make the younger generation well-rounded people. is upbringing. Of course, to be a perfect person is to be spiritually mature caring for the history, present and future of the homeland, as well as has contributed to the economic development of society, is eager to contribute understanding the Burning Person is in line with today's demand. Highlight the future of any society depends on how the younger generation is educated and depends on how you are brought up. Only such a generation is in front of the country able to perform tasks of national importance determines the historical destiny of its people.

In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan expressed the following views "We have all the links in the education system today," he said it is our priority to improve in line with modern requirements we know. Speaking about the upbringing of the younger generation, Abdurauf Fitrat is our ancestor I would like every one of us, especially our sons and daughters, to follow this idea. This is our great ancestor "The people must strive for a clear goal, to become rich, to be happy, to be honored, to be a warrior, or to be humiliated by being weak to fall, to bear the burden of unhappiness, to be neglected, to be enslaved and enslaved It depends on the upbringing he received from his parents. " The issue of educating a comprehensively mature, harmoniously developed generation is becoming an important object of study in all areas of science that exist in our lives today. This, in turn, raises a number of pressing theoretical and practical issues for each science and its experts.

Therefore, this process does not bypass the science of psychology, on the contrary, it also applies to the modern science of psychology, which determines its research areas according to the daily needs and orders of society. Projective methods of studying the individual in the science and practice of psychology has a special place. The person in

his emergence and development, his inner psychological views on the idea of the possibility of knowing the world evolution.

Projective psychology with a history of half a century of development is one of the fields of psychological knowledge about man today it is impossible to form a holistic view of the Person without mastering it. The projective method of personality research is to identify and describe projections based on.

The concept of "projection" was first introduced by Z. Freud to the subject's consciousness and unconsciously copied personal properties in relation to external objects used to describe the content of cases. Projection Latin Derived from the word "proektio", which means to throw forward, to throw. The projective method of studying the person is based on the results of the experiment identifies projections and then analyzes them. The description of the concept of projection is inextricably linked with the protective mechanisms of the "I". Projection sublimation, rationalization (reasoning to justify one's actions, reasoning) find), catharsis (cleansing) as well as one of the protective mechanisms considered.

Projective methods put the subject in a position where he or she can His personal needs, his unique perceptions, descriptions, and many personalities properties. Projection word associations, incomplete sentences, pictures and spots, verbal as well as drawings drawn by the examinee observed using all pictorial methods. To projective methodologies The most important features are:

- A relatively unstructured and varied response consists of staging tasks;
- Non-uniform, scattered, unordered stimuli act as a "screen" for personality traits, status and problems;
- To identify and evaluate the hidden, misunderstood aspects of the person the breadth of the approach.

Projective methods to measure personality traits and intelligence oriented material from standardized methods the nature of the respondent, i.e., the task set before the respondent, and the difference in the nature of the processing and interpretation of the results does.

Projection Perception of reality, people, manifested stimuli is to some extent based on the mental state, needs, motives, attitudes of the person. In this case, the reality depends on the mental state, needs, characteristics of the person there is a tendency to describe accordingly. The projection is psychologically misunderstood is a mechanism, that is, the elements of projection are perceived unconsciously. The main feature of projective methods is that they are used that stimuli are ambiguous and ambiguous. However, it is recommended to the examiner stimulus (regardless of image, color, spot, verbal information) vague, ambiguous, yet objective in nature and subjective an image created by or a specific that is included in the situation that has arisen features. The results obtained are the knowledge of the person being examined, it based on in-depth

psychological study, as well as psychodiagnostics should be described using other methods.

The history of projective methods was created by K. Yung in 1904-1905 based on the verbal associations test. By creating this methodology, K. Yung Associative diagnosis of a person's experiences of unconsciousness showed that it is possible. Later, different variants of the associative test were used to identify guilt (lie detector, M. Wertheimer and L.R. Luria), used to separate the norm from pathology, and so on.

Incomplete that the story or speech test is also derived from K. Jung's associative test is The Origins of Projective Diagnostics in 1921 by G. Rorschach Bernda is associated with the publication of Psychodiagnostics in German. Despite being an artist himself, German Rorschach has a history of art and painting more interested. It turned out that the great Leonardo da Vinci was his own imagining the clouds in the sky, the various shapes in them for a long time and trained them by analyzing them. It's a feature that surrounds us "reviving" the subject world to everyone, especially artists and young children feature.

Projective methodologies are diverse. They are radically different from each other. However, it should be noted that the description of the projective methodology is specific psychological practical application of knowledge, special theoretical training and methodology requires experience.

There is a growing focus on projective methods The number of scientific articles devoted to it has exceeded 6,000. But also they have become a constant target for criticism. Other than psychodiagnostics Unlike methods, projective methods quantify personality traits rather than qualitative analysis. That's why no methods have been developed to verify their reliability and validity. L. Frank (1939,1948) was one of the first to use projective methods as follows classified by:

1. Constitutional methodologies - what the subject is presented to him giving subjective content to amorphous, disordered, unstructured material will need This group uses projective methods such as Rorschach's "Ink Spots methodology", Varteg's "Circles" methodology.
2. Constructive methodologies - recommendation to the examiner during the experiment has a specific meaning using the individual parts (shapes, cubes) provided must form a whole object and interpret it;
3. Interpretive methods - the proposed sheet, the event to be examined or asked to comment on the incident;
4. Cathartic methodologies. The word cathartic means "cleansing." In psychoanalysis, using the catharsis method, the individual has an existing negative protected from re-experiencing experiences. This of projective methodologies various life situations that are examined in the form of a game or psychodrama managed to bring out his inner experiences through reflection ("Psychodrama").

5. Expressive methods - hidden through the visual activity being tested, expresses motives and relationships under pressure (writing, drawing images are analyzed). The secret of the person using these methods changes in the text or letter by the subject of the motives determined on the basis of ("Non-existent animal", "House, tree, man", "Man drawing a picture", "Kinetic picture of a family")

6. Impressive methods are recommended for the subject will have to choose between the pleasant and the unpleasant from the stimuli. For example, turning on the 8 colored squares recommended to him by the subject in the Luscher test will need to be placed in order according to the level. The colors are selected instead; a conclusion is drawn about the most important needs of the individual. ("Zondi tests")

7. Additive methods. Additivity - a whole object or property is a characteristic of size, even if it is divided into smaller components or the property remains its own. In this type of projective methodologies, the examinee is required to complete the sentence or story that began. This methodologies ranging from changes in a person's life to behavioral motives as well to the attitudes of young people towards sex education. ("Incomplete sentences", "Incomplete pictures") There are many methods used in modern projective psychodiagnostics a lot. M.K. According to Akimova, these methods are widespread their structuring, constructing, interpreting, supplementing, catharsis, expression, and impression. The number of publications on the technique of using this or that projective methodology and more than 6,000.

However, in most cases, the objectivity of projective methods is sufficient criticize for not. Projective methodologies despite the presence of certain shortcomings The reason for its growing popularity is, firstly, by the examiner lack of possibility of falsification; second, the effectiveness of the subject's communication (especially with children) In conclusion, the introduction of the ideas of experimentation and measurement in the field of psychology in the composition of the scientific Testology, in particular, on the scientific and practical issues of personality psychology, can be considered a major step in the field of research. A clear example of this can be seen in the long-standing research of the German scientist Wolf in the 1930s on the identification of attentional features. Projective methodologies focus on measuring personality traits and intelligence, and vary in the way they process and interpret results.

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EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF VOLLEYBALL IN UZBEKISTAN

Mirzambetov Polat Sherniyazovich
Senior Lecturer at Nukus State Pedagogical Institute

Kazakov Shavkat Norkobilovich
Tashkent State Pedagogical University
Named After Nizami University Teacher

Annotation

This article has a unique history of development in Uzbekistan, its regions and districts, which reflects the development and origin of the sport of volleyball. Although volleyball is one of the most popular sports in Uzbekistan, it has gained “prestige” at various levels in all regions of the country.

Keywords: Volleyball, physical education, sports, independent, prestige, competition, rule, game.

Introduction

Volleyball is one of the largest and most independent streams of the system of physical culture and sports, and has a unique history of development in Uzbekistan, its regions and districts. Although volleyball is one of the most popular sports in Uzbekistan, it has gained “prestige” at various levels in all regions of the country. In the city of Tashkent and Tashkent region, in the towns and villages of the valley, volleyball has gained more effective "respect" than in other districts of the region. Although it is assumed that the reasons for this situation are almost related to the historical and social foundations of these regions, the issue requires in-depth research, the study of the historical background of the subject on a scientific basis. There is no exact information about when, where and under what conditions volleyball appeared in Uzbekistan. However, according to some estimates, in 1921-24, volleyball began to appear in Kokand, Tashkent and Fergana. According to the story of K. Lebedev, a sports veteran of the urban period, in 1924-25, many young people began to spread the game of passing the ball to each other in a circle. Interestingly, the rules of international volleyball competitions adopted during this period have been significantly improved, the field is 9x18 m, the ball can be played only 11 times, the composition of the players consists of 6 people in a team, to ' mi height 243 5m (men uchlln), the end of a part of the game when the score reaches 15 points, putting the ball into play - in short. all the rules of the game were similar to the rules of the modern volleyball game. Nevertheless, the rules of volleyball in Uzbekistan in 1924-25 were still quite simple. VI Perevoznikov, a sports fan at the time, said that in 1926 he was a teacher at the Chemishevsky School in Tashkent. tournament rules, volleyball net and brought the ball for the first time. On April 26,

1927, the volleyball team of the same school organized the first official competition, in which he showed great skill and won the competition. This tournament marked a turning point in the popularization and formation of volleyball. In one of the summer months of 1927, the Tashkent city volleyball championship was held, which was attended by 9 volleyball teams. The Chernyshevsky school volleyball team also won the tournament. The popularity of volleyball was greatly influenced by the competitions held at the KIM Stadium. In 1992, there were 6 volleyball courts in Tashkent, which were located in Chernyshevsky and KIM schools, Mechanics College (2), Metallist Sports Club and Protintern Summer Sports Club. In 1928, Tashkent hosted a volleyball tournament, which was attended by 1,018 men's and 4 women's teams. Since 1929, the Tashkent city volleyball championship has been held regularly. In the 1930s, volleyball teams were formed at the Dynamo Voluntary Sports Association. The first coach of the first volleyball team "Dynamo" BA Vorollsov made a significant contribution to the development of volleyball in Uzbekistan. At the same time, there is a lack of qualified specialists, especially local instructors. the paucity of coaches and organizers has prevented volleyball from flourishing in remote provinces and villages. In order to attract workers, especially women, to physical culture and sports, including volleyball, the Tashkent City Council together with the Tashkent District Committee organized a national practical week from April 25 to May 15, 1929. This event has yielded significant results. In particular, there has been a sharp increase in the number of people involved in physical education and sports, most of whom play volleyball. The construction of volleyball courts and other sports facilities in many places has gained momentum. Particular attention was paid to training and professional development of specialists. On September 30, 1929 in Samarkand were trained instructors-organizers in physical culture and sports, consisting of young people of local ethnicity. In 1933, the Spartakiad of Uzbekistan was held. and in the women's competition, the Uztrans team took first place1934 was an important turning point for Uzbek volleyball.) In particular, for the first time Uzbek volleyball players He took part in the national championship in Moscow. In the same year, volleyball was included in the Central Asian and Kazakh Spaltakiad program for the first time. In addition, a large gym for volleyball training and competitions was opened at the Tashkent Institute of Finance and Economics. A volleyball school for 60 people was opened in Samarkand by the decision of the city administration and the city council. It should be noted that for the first time in the development of Uzbek volleyball A. Saakov, G.L. Keshishev, V.Kh.Slmurov, V.F.Shveduks, A.A.Bogachenko, B.A. The services of coaches like Vorontsov are of particular importance. Modern classical volleyball has acquired a new meaning since the end of the XX century and the XXI century due to its natural development and drastic changes in the rules of the competition. A radical change in the rules of the game is determined not only by the competition of the winning teams, but also to a certain extent by market relations.

It is known that in the conduct of major prestigious competitions (World, Asian Championships, Olympics, Asian Games and other high-rated international competitions, Cups), many TV and radio companies, Jumalists specialize in telecasting these competitions, reporting. must meet the accreditation requirement.

If the intensity of the game in the mentioned competitions is slow, the points are often taken due to "strong" blows, and the continuous process is often interrupted and there are many stops, the interest in the competition disappears. begins, the accreditation market is limited, the audience begins to shrink. This was the case until 1996-98. Because according to the old rules, the "kuchii" forwards located in the defensive zones "worked" the points as a result of jumping sharply from the 4th or 2nd zone without pressing the offensive and side lines. The game is stopped when the ball touches the legs and waist. If the ball falls far from the field, time is running out, it is forbidden to play with another ball, if the ball is "lost", the opposing team is not given points, if the ball hits the net, the game was stopped, and so on. These situations often cause the game to stop.

Many of the fundamental changes in today's volleyball rules have eliminated such "stops". In particular, the game will be played with the participation of 3 goals (one goal in the game, 2 goals in reserve). It is bordered by 1.75 m off-field lines from the intersection of the sideline and the offensive line. It is allowed to play with any part of the body. The game will be played as a tie-break, which means that points will be awarded to the opposing team even if the ball is "lost". The "force" of the rule of receiving or passing the "first" ball has been sharply relaxed, and if the ball hits the net, it will be considered "correct".

Such a change in the rules of the competition dramatically accelerated the intensity of the game, increased the activity of the players, increased the interest of the audience.

It should be noted that the radical change in the rules of the competition has further enriched the content of the game, giving rise to a completely new generation of game modes. In particular, strikes from defensive zones focused on the need to master the quality of diagonal jumps, the establishment of a "libero" player strengthened the defense, running and jumping increased the pace of attack, and so on. The new elements of the game, the special qualities, the methods of movement that have emerged as a result of these changes, highlight the importance of a new approach to the content of training, the introduction of new exercises and ensuring the unity of training and competition.

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COMMUNICATION OF SECONDARY PARTS OF SPEECH WITH PARENTHESES

Muhiddinova Dilafruz Mansurovna

Teacher of English Language and Literature, Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

Annotation

The article is scientifically based on the syntactic relationship of parenthesis units with complement and determiner. The semantic connection of word-form, phrase, and sentence-in-parent parentheses is substantiated using examples from the work of art.

Keywords: Filler, determiner, parenthesis, word, phrase, compound sentence, semantic aspect.

Introduction

Parentheses that are in direct contact with the filler can also have structurally different forms:

1. The word-form parentheses are directly related to the filler: His conclusion was erroneous. The ambassador did not expect or even dream of such a gift. If he wants, he can buy such a car in half a year. Even if Zaynab told someone that she was not happy, she would burn this "gift" (or "debt") so that she would not accept it (Tahir Malik, the novel "Satan"). Apparently, the parentheses have been interpreting the meaning of the instrumental filler (this "gift").

The toolless filler can also be used in some cases in an unmarked state. In such cases, the parentheses that are semantically connected are also in the form of a filler without an unknown means: God bless you, amen oblohu akbar. He held four chachvan (chimmat) in his son's hand (G. Gulom, the story of "Farzandi Salih"). In addition to the meaning of the parenthesis introduced, it can also be used interchangeably with the filler with which it is associated. This does not harm the semantic content of the speech fragment.

As a result of our observations, it should be noted that when parentheses perform a specific filler function and interact with a filler in the main context, in most cases they have the same grammatical index as the filler he interprets and receive the same question:) is afraid. She is afraid that her family will be ruined ... Zaynab is not of that category. She is not afraid of her husband or her family breaking up (Tahir Malik, Satan). The number is written in black lacquer ("Kuzbaslak") that does not fade in the sun or in the rain (Said Ahmad, the story of "Sarob").

2. The parenthesis in the form of a phrase is directly related to the filler: He stared at his wife (not at his wife, but at himself in his image!) With his eyes wide open (Khurshid Dostmuhammad, The Story of the House at the Foot). When he opened the fridge in the

morning (his only wealth) and saw that there was nothing worthwhile for breakfast, his mood became gloomy (Zulfiya Kuroloy qizi, "Love and Hate" story).

Sometimes in an artistic context, the author also expresses his artistic-aesthetic intention by using words belonging to a lexicon with a limited scope of consumption. In particular, the use of dialectal words gives the speech a local color, and the image of the protagonist is fully reflected in the eyes of the reader. In order to make these words understandable to the general public, the author also introduces their equivalent form in the form of a compound: Only the patient had reached the point where he could not clench his fist, bleeding and fainting. He replaced the wound with melon (burnt cotton) (G. Gulom, the story of "Luqman").

3. The parenthesis in the form of a simple sentence is in direct contact with the filler. Brackets in the form of simple sentences are characterized by the fact that they are the product of the author's subjective relations, such as emphasis and emphasis on additional information: He worked in the district, not in Dashtsaroy) with his wife Sohobakhan (O. Yakubov, the novel "Swans, white birds"). Bakir now remembers this horrible incident and believes that his father-in-law met a witch (if she really was a witch!) (Erkin Azam, the story "Days other than the holiday").

4. The parentheses in the form of a compound sentence are directly related to the filler: The bride and groom went to the market on the way and bought a cake from the gastronome "Ptiche moloko" ("Barnosha sees this, she will die!") And a bunch of telpaksimons chrysanthemums days" story).

It is in this situation that parentheses can be included in the text even in an unobstructed following sentence pattern. In this case, the parentheses mean that the condition for the occurrence of the action expressed in the filler to which it is connected is not an obstacle to the fulfillment of the action in the main sentence: Marjonoy ... did not know where to put himself. In this state he could hardly bear it until noon, and then his heart was pounding, and he decided to go to the office and wire the city (though he could not imagine who would wire it). (O. Yakubov, the novel "Address of Justice"). The word though was also used to emphasize and exaggerate the barrier-free condition in parentheses in the unobstructed following sentence pattern.

In some cases, parentheses in the form of a compound sentence may also be associated with non-functional complements within the construction governed by the functional forms of the verb in the main sentence (adjective, adverb, noun): (Ideally, Erkin Azam, The Poet's Wedding), remembering the sweet moments he had with him - trips to the "great capital" and vacations on the shores of the Black Sea. The word form with Tepakali in the example is a non-functional complement within the adjective-controlled construction, and the compound sentence form is now explained by parentheses in the form in which it has become rosmana kalga, but in all respects preferred any curly hair.

5. The parenthesis in the form of a microtext is in direct contact with the filler. In certain cases, the writer encloses a certain part of the information that he considers important

in the form of parentheses in the context using punctuation marks, linking the content only with the filler with which he is communicating. In such cases, the parentheses are in the form of microtext. In early 1917, Yusufjonboy, without thinking about where to use it, bought thirteen wagons at a low price on the recommendation of a merchant on the Moscow side, hoping that it would be of some benefit.

(The support is the head, not the left side of the boot. Those who take off the boots of the dead soldiers, cut off the boots and make the head useless, are the thrown part of the boot.) (Ghafur Ghulam, The Story of Hajj Accepted).

The author referred to the microtext of parentheses in the detailed description of the filler (support) represented by the name in the main text. It is in parentheses in the form of this microtext that the writer's artistic goals, such as interpretation and additional information, were demonstrated.

III. Parentheses that are directly related to the determinant can also be structurally different:

1. The parentheses in the form of words are directly related to the determiner: The intention of the adults in our family (including me) these days was to hold the ceremony as soon as possible and as full as everyone could see (A. Islamov, "Missing" story). The grammatical form of the word-parentheses may or may not be the same as the grammatical form of the word in the determinative position, as in this example (the accusative case): ... I saw men in black coats (Sh. Kholmiraev, the story "The sun is wandering in the sky").

2. The parenthesis in the form of a phrase is directly connected with the determiner: The windows of the house on the other side (Omon's house) are open, a yellow curtain hangs, but it is clear that no one is inside (O. Hoshimov, "Between Two Doors"). When Fatima-Zuhra, the bride of Rashid abzi, was returning, when my brother Kimsan tried to beat my brother Achil, on the wedding day of my uncle Shomurod (now Shomurod aka, who is now my husband), we both went to Tashkent to watch. . . my star was next to me (O. Hoshimov, the novel "Between Two Doors"). As can be seen, the grammatical form of the determiner and the parentheses in the main sentence are the same (accusative case). This is not, of course, permanent, and these grammatical forms may be different. The following examples are proof of this: The rain had already subsided, and now the wind was blowing in this calm, the smell of the waking trees was reminiscent of my people, and the poor moon was passing in front of the clouds ... (Sh.) What if in France he met a believer who wore this simple suit and trousers for five or six years and listened in silence to his wife's poison (especially when it came to money)?! (Zulfiya Kuroilboy qizi, the story of the "Angel of Evil").

Sometimes parentheses are also used to express the meaning of an adjective that is not expressed in the main sentence, with a special emphasis on the determinative meaning of parentheses: Biydek field, cotton field. A hundred paces away, at the beginning of the border, there is a trailer (now it looks like a trailer crossing the road) (O. Hoshimov,

“Uzbek affair” story). This parenthesis compensates for the meaning of the unexpressed determiner of the possessive in the main sentence.

3. The parentheses in the form of a simple sentence are directly related to the determinant: Salomatkhan's father kissed the forehead of the old man with a black eyebrow, black eyes, and a happy old man's beard (Said Ahmad, "I'm looking for"). In the example, the parentheses in the form of a simple spread sentence are associated with an expanded compound adjective-determiner (which does not detract from the beard-mustache mill), which determines the characteristics of the owner (old man).

The parentheses included in the text with the intention of the writer may also be in the form of a simple summary sentence. For example: An old woman from the front row, whose life was called make-up, whose hair was still black (dyed), who seemed to have died in her youth, and who was clearly shiny, stood up and bowed to Allanechuk with pleasure and disappointment (Erkin A'zam). , "The Poet's Wedding" story).

The adjective-determiner (the hair is still black) in the given main sentence is associated with a simple compound sentence-shaped parenthesis. This identifier is associated with the possessive represented by the word old woman, logically the old woman's hair cannot be black, so an explanation is needed. The comment is made by means of a painted bracket, which clearly shows its direct relevance to the determinant.

It is often observed that the meaning of the determiner in the main sentence is the concrete clarity of the parentheses in the form of a sentence. For example, after E. Safar's failed (unconfirmed facts!) Critical article, this creature, which everyone started calling "Kattakon's puppy", is not a silent fox or a furry dog, but a tiger! (Erkin Azam, the story of "Aralashkurgan"). The failure-style identifier is further defined by parentheses.

Thus, the use of parentheses directly related to parts of speech in a literary text is very diverse and complex, and the cases discussed above are just the basics. We do not deny that there are too many special cases in this, in accordance with the artistic intent of the writer.

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BRIEF HISTORICAL INFORMATION ABOUT THE ANCIENT WORLD AND MODERN SPORTS FACILITIES

Utepbergenova Aysara Jaksimuratovna

Assistant Teacher of the Faculty of Physical Culture of NDPI Named After Ajiniyaz

Annotation:

This article briefly describes the ancient sports facilities and modern sports facilities. The construction of sports facilities is developing rapidly in our country.

Keywords: Student, youth, education, health, sports, physical education, sports facility, competition, complex, task.

Introduction

The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. A. Karimov spoke with great pride about the great value of public health and the ways to achieve it in the future. That is, "When our ancestors met or said goodbye to people, first of all, they sincerely wished them good health. These traditions are a rich heritage of our time for our heroes and defenders, and they are nurtured with love. Today, national sports are being revived everywhere. The culture of personal care should be instilled in young people with the help of schools, neighborhoods, health care, physical education and sports organizations," he said.

The national physical culture of the Uzbek people is inextricably linked with the history of our ancient ancestors. As noted in the previous chapter, courage is praised in the epics of the series "Alpomish", "Kuntugmush", "Kirgiz", "Gorogly". Physical qualities such as horse racing, javelin throwing, fencing, archery and sniping reflect the life, culture and movement of the whole nation through the image of heroes. These exercises have been passed down from generation to generation, enriching their content, form and methods of performance, and today they have become a favorite pastime of the peoples of the world and a sport of young people fighting for mastery. It should be noted that the most important measures are being taken to further develop physical culture and sports in independent Uzbekistan. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Physical Culture and Sports" (January 14, 1992, new edition) guarantees the strengthening of health of the entire population, the creation of conditions for their participation in physical culture and sports. At the same time, the law states that "Preschools and universities conduct physical examinations of preschool children and students at least once a year. Physical education exams are held in secondary schools and other educational institutions." It aims to improve the health of students, increase their physical development, and train them to be able to work and defend themselves. Every student should understand these opportunities and activities with their own minds, do their best to contribute to the future of independent

Uzbekistan and fulfill their duties. It is known that the Law "On Education" (July 1992, new edition 1997) was adopted at the session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic. called The content and essence of these two laws are intertwined and are aimed at the development of physical culture and sports. The education and constant health of students should be interpreted as protecting them by state law and ensuring a bright future for future professionals. As a result, all students, wherever they study, will need to take advantage of the benefits provided to them, to ensure their physical development, and thus to further the social and historical significance of physical education, to inherit it as a high factor in human life. practice is the basis. Therefore, one of the important tasks is to be aware of the state of the main sources of the future of sports in the country and the factors of its development. While international sports events (competitions) were not held in Uzbekistan before independence, in recent years our country has gained a reputation as a country capable of hosting the largest international competitions at a high organizational level.

The construction of modern sports facilities allows us to hold the largest international competitions in our country. Sports facilities are the material and technical basis of physical education. They are specially constructed facilities for physical education in all sports. After independence, it was said that children are the backbone of our great future. Raising a healthy generation begins in early childhood. Physical education, especially sports, plays an important role in this. The subject of "sports facilities" is a part of it at the stage of sports pedagogy. At this stage, in order to study science, it is necessary to have a certain knowledge of sports hygiene, biomechanics, pedagogy, theory and methods of physical education.

Sports facilities are a multifaceted cultural and health-improving sports complex for special activities. Sports grounds, swimming pools, maneges and other facilities are built in the country for training and public events. The planning of sports facilities in the Republic of Uzbekistan is also included in the national program. experiences and development. At present, great attention is paid to the development of sports in our country. Therefore, it is necessary to find solutions to such issues as planning in the construction of sports facilities, which should meet today's requirements. The historical roots of physical education and sports have long been known. Archaeological excavations have revealed that sports were also practiced in the Stone Age. This is based on the discovery of sports facilities in historical excavations. (India, Arabia, Central Asia and South America). From ancient times, scientists have been well aware of the importance of physical education. Physical education and sports are the main sources of health, improving the ability of workers to develop productive forces. History has shown that sports competitions were held in ancient Greece. Each city had sports facilities for these competitions. Archaeological excavations have also proved this. For example, excavations in Mycenae, Crete, on the shores of the Aegean Sea, depict various games, exercises, and disputes. Exercise was used for military physical

training. The beginning of the Middle Ages was characterized by a complete decline in physical education. The reason for this is, first of all, Christianity. According to Christianity, the culture and all-round development of the human body was denied. As a state religion, many stadiums and sports facilities were illegally demolished. However, in the tenth and eleventh centuries, sports and exercise gradually began to develop. This was due to the trade conquests of the East in the 11th century, marches, and the emergence of knights. In their spare time, knights practiced military exercises and participated in tournaments. The bourgeois regime took over the economies of European countries and took over political power. Capitalist production was able to create large sports facilities in rapidly developing countries. The largest of these was the Milan Sports Arena, built in 1806-1807. In the middle of the 19th century, large gyms were built in Europe (railway stations, department stores, etc.). Gyms and playgrounds appeared. However, the construction of public sports facilities in various European countries began at the end of the 19th century, when sports societies, clubs, and other countries established contacts, developed sports ties, and hosted the Olympic Games. During this period, not only stadiums and gyms were built, but also facilities for cycling tracks, springboards, winter and summer water sports. In the study of Olympic sports facilities, we understand the basic technological requirements for them, and over time, we understand that the construction of sports facilities in different countries has developed. Categories of sports facilities are determined in accordance with the Ministry of Physical Culture and Sports. Categories I and II are determined by the republican sports committees, the rest by the regional and district committees. Many sports facilities are being built not only in cities, but also in district and regional centers and villages. It gathers people in mass physical culture and treatment centers and prepares young people for work and defense of the Motherland. Great work has been done in our country to develop the material and technical base of physical culture and sports. In particular, Tashkent, Namangan, Fergana, Bukhara, Khorezm, Andijan, Samarkand, Gulistan and others. A number of sports complexes meeting international standards have been built in the cities. Among them are Yunusabad in Tashkent, Jar, the National Bank, Pahlavon in Namangan, sports complexes of the College of Olympic Reserve in Jizzakh and others. By 2000, the number of sports facilities in the country reached 7,407, an increase of 19% compared to 1992. Particular attention is paid to the construction of complex sports facilities - stadiums, swimming pools, gyms.

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METHODS OF SHAPING THE CULTURE OF THE TEACHER

Shovqiyeva Shokhida Bobosher qizi

Student of the Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture

Abstract

This article highlights social science, the level of teacher training in globalization, its professional and personal qualities, values, attitudes and interests, professional development of one's thinking, emotional development, skills and competence, methodological aspects of teacher culture.

Keywords: integration process, “cultural person” teacher, abilities, thinking, competence, teacher culture.

Introduction

The processes of globalization of the cultural and educational space taking place in the world, of which integrative processes are a past, carry a great potential for the development of humanitarian education in our country. The prospects for its renewal make it urgent to prepare a professional who is capable of ing his own activities in various sociocultural situations, ready to find ways to solve problems arising regardless of particular circumstances, to develop a special strategy for professional thinking, behavior and activity.

Requirements for the level of training of the teacher, his professional and personal qualities, values, attitudes and interests, professional orientation of thinking, emotional-volitional qualities, abilities and competencies are steadily increasing. Orientation to n-functionalism in the preparation and thinking of a specialist is a thing of the past. A teacher - an employee of a secondary and higher vocational school, needs a holistic orientation in the human world, which implies the development of his own value-semantic sphere, openness to the world and the impact of culture. Hence, the main condition for the implementation of these requirements, which determine the guidelines for secondary and higher education, is the transition to a new educational paradigm, the dominant factor of which is culture, the upbringing of “a person of culture”.

Material and Methods

The culture of the teacher can be considered as a specific way of realizing the individual qualities of a person. Variability, resourcefulness, the ability to generate ideas, courage, initiative, unconventional ideas - this is not a complete list of human features that allow him to effectively carry out and creative activities.

In a modern technocratic society, the development of which is characterized by extraordinary mobility, variability, the project type of culture begins to dominate, becoming one of the central mechanisms of future creation, revealing the universal and synthetic nature of project activity, in which a combination of technocratic and humane, research and prognostic, informational educational and socio-transformative principles, and this leads to the fact that each teacher needs I can master the activity in its various versions. The of not only the pedagogical process, but also the pedagogical system as a whole, especially its methodological component, is one of the important components of the teacher's professional and pedagogical activity.

Results and Discussion

In modern scientific literature, researchers identify various methodological approaches to the analysis of the problem of the formation of the culture of teachers. As leaders, one can distinguish: the ideas of the integrity and systematic nature of the pedagogical process, as well as the activity- parametric and task approach to pedagogical activity. We give a brief description of these approaches in the context of the research problem. As noted by modern research teachers [2; 7; 8], if as a result of paradigmatic self-determination we understand the essence of the educational process as a process of "personality formation in the sense of its formation, creation, selfrealization", then the formation of a project culture, along with traditional training, plays the most significant role in this. The definition of culture formulated by us in relation to the definition of personality given by K. K. Platonov fully confirms the conclusion made.

According to K. K. Platonov [5], "a person is an actively mastering and purposefully transforming nature, society and himself a person who has a unique, dynamic ratio of spatio-temporal orientations, need-volitional experiences, meaningful orientations, levels of development and forms implementation of activities that ensure freedom of self-determination in actions and a measure of responsibility for their consequences to nature, society and their conscience." The signs contained in this definition perfectly convey the essence of what is happening in the real process of joint with students.

The process of creating a culture can be considered from different points of view. It can be characterized as an action consisting of elements: the objective side, i.e. method (method) of the action; subjective side, i.e. the relationship of the subject to the action and its result, and the subject himself performing the action. A dynamic approach is productive for us, which will allow us to study the behavior and activities of the teacher in development.

An analysis of the experience of educators and practitioners has led to the conclusion that the process of forming a project culture is a complex, contradictory and at the same time regular process of self-movement of a person, in which the stages of nucleation, formation, and perfection go through (the absence of the latter can lead to process damping). The driving force of the process of formation of project culture is the

motivation of the subjects of the educational process, manifested in their desire for personal reflective professionalism, self-realization.

One of the central questions in the study of the process of formation of a project culture is the question of personality mechanisms that ensure ascent to a project culture. Based on the analysis of the works of A. V. Kiryakova [2], P. Titer [6] and others, an assumption was made about the need to integrate research mechanisms - evaluation - self-determination - goal-setting - action.

The main determinants that define the specific tasks of creating a project culture are:

- 1) Movement towards independence and individuality; in its most general form, this vector defines the discontinuity of continuous development in the general process as a sequence of its stages and steps;
- 2) The project and program for organizing the educational process as a special (leading) form of development activity;
- 3) Intermediate results of the general course of development as normatively ed individual abilities that provide reflection;
- 4) Socio-pedagogical of the educational environment in which the relevant processes are implemented [3].

Turning to the mechanisms of the formation of a project culture, we note that, in the opinion of V. I. Chemobytov [8], they include not just all areas of pedagogical activity: research, educational, educational, managerial, but their complex relationship.

The research area requires the development of the theoretical foundations of the phenomenon of project culture, the identification of personality traits that have mastered the culture, principles, patterns, conditions for the formation of a new type of culture, the development of diagnostic procedures. The area is aimed at creating a pedagogical system of the educational organization, focused on the formation of the culture of the subjects of the educational process and a description of the technology of its functioning. Educational - focuses on specially organized, focused and controlled interaction of the administration, the team of educators and pupils with the aim of forming a project culture and social maturity as generalized results of personality development for all participants in the educational process. Educational - focused on the inclusion of projective education technologies directly in the learning process, both in basic and in additional educational programs. Management - requires the adoption of organizational and pedagogical decisions on the introduction of projective education in the life of an educational organization.

The formation of the project culture of the teacher is impossible without the value-semantic self-determination of the subjects of the pedagogical process in the humanistic paradigm, since it is in its context that what constitutes the value basis for self-determination of any subject of the pedagogical process [4]. And if, as a result of paradigmatic self-determination in the context of the humanitarian paradigm, we understand the essence of the educational process as a process of “personality

formation in the sense of its formation, creation, self-realization”, then the formation of a project culture, along with traditional training, plays the most significant role in this [7,8,8,9,10,11].

It should be noted that the process of the formation of a project culture, if we really want it to make profound, essential changes in the personality, is impossible without self-determination of subjects in the humanistic paradigm, their understanding of the concept of “personality”, creation of conditions for mastering the project culture. Without such awareness, without reflection, aimed at developing the need for mastering the project culture in oneself, it hardly makes sense to start interacting with students to develop real projects. In this regard, of particular importance is the problem of realizing the creative potential of the subjects of the educational process.

One of the productive ways to solve this problem is to build the content of activities for the formation of the experience of creative activity as a component of the culture based on the implementation of the activity-parametric approach. From the point of view of E.V. Berezhnova [1], the experience of creative activity includes the following substantial components:

1. Ing and ing activities, involving: the ability to the content of future activities; ability to a system and sequence of own actions; the ability to a system and the sequence of actions of other participants in the process.
2. Awareness, formulation and creative solution of tasks, including the ability to: see the problem and correlate factual material with it; express the problem in a specific task; put forward a hypothesis and carry out a thought experiment; clearly see several different possible paths and mentally choose the most effective; distribute the solution into “steps” in the optimal sequence.
3. Pedagogical reflection is not so much a statement of the presence or absence of a project culture as stimulation of its development, enrichment, and strengthening.
4. The experience of pedagogical reflection, integrating introspection, included in the direct activities carried out during the process, self-observation, self-control, self-esteem; retrospective introspection of the past; predictive introspection facing the future: self-foresight, self-commitment, self-report.

The essence of the implementation of the activity-parametric approach is that:

- 1) A special emphasis in the formation of the experience of creative activity is placed on the organization of independent cognitive and practical activities of the subjects of the educational process to solve problems associated with the development and implementation of a social project, allowing to maximize the value orientations of the subjects of the process in the course of activities that are creative in nature;
- 2) When selecting, developing or implementing a social project, each parameter of its quality (goal setting, value-semantic self-determination of ers, choice of logic, etc.) acts as a special task of analysis, planning, execution and control by its participants. It must be emphasized that the parametric approach allows the formation of knowledge and

skills of a sufficiently high level of generalization, which contributes to their wide transfer, providing the necessary conditions for independent creative activity.

The formation of a system of mental and practical actions is an important task in establishing a culture. Such a system is necessary for the awareness of independent work, the implementation of purposeful activities, the choice of methods for achieving goals and evaluating the results. In other words, each of the subjects involved in the educational process should be adequately prepared for individual or collective development and implementation of a specific project. The results of project activities should be recorded in the form of a description of the methods, goals and conditions for their achievement, considering social, pedagogical and economic feasibility. This condition describes the productively oriented nature of the activity. In addition, it is necessary to clearly fix the pedagogical result of the activity, for the working materials on the implemented activities, as well as the project itself, together give an idea of the level of ownership of the project culture.

However, it must be remembered that the project culture is formed in stages and the effectiveness of this process is revealed in the implementation of reflective management of it. The project culture of the teacher is assessed as the basis of the dynamic strategy of its formation and development, and the internal processes of the intellectual, emotional-volitional, personal development of the future teacher, up to the beginning of his professional activity, imply setting goals for the formation of the project culture. This approach is supported by the general orientation that it is the project culture that today ensures the high efficiency of the professional activity of teaching staff [8]. In addition, the formation of the culture of a teacher of a modern educational organization is an indispensable component of the professional training of highly qualified and competitive specialists in demand on the labor market.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, the methodological approaches identified in the research form a single methodological complex, which allowed us to holistically present the problem of the formation of the project culture of the teacher and consistently approach it in line with the trends of modern secondary and higher education, aimed at creating the necessary conditions for educating the person who creates the future : focus on creating a developing educational environment; changing the target orientation of the education system to the formation of a project culture; the transition from mass, collective forms of education to individual; development of creative and abilities.

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INCREASING THE INTEREST OF STUDENTS WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITIES TO THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

Pulatova P. M.

Tashkent State Pedagogical University Named After Nizami, Faculty of Special
Pedagogy and Inclusive Education, Professor of the Department of
Oligophrenopedagogy, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences

Raximova Kamola Xōjamberdiyevna
2nd Year Master Student

Annotation

The article emphasizes the need to increase the interest of students with intellectual disabilities in cognition, the help of an oligophrenopedagogue for schoolchildren, to actively comprehend their knowledge, to actively solve cognitive problems, to understand the nature and logic of the learning process, its essence.

Keywords: Students with intellectual disabilities, cognition, interest in knowledge, logic, active integration into society, correctional and pedagogical, knowledge acquisition, educational process, academic work, leadership.

Introduction

From the first years of independence, the education and upbringing of children with physical or mental disabilities has been identified as a priority in the education system of our country. In particular, Article 41 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan enshrines the right of everyone to education.

Today, the growing importance of the social approach to the concept of "disability" contrasts sharply with the need to create a separate category of society that needs not only the help of others, but also the elimination of its shortcomings from the earliest stages of development. It is also recognized that the study of the possibilities of active integration into society and socialization should contribute to the formation of a person as capable of meeting the needs of various areas through correctional and pedagogical technologies and methods. (Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On approval of regulatory legal acts on specialized state educational institutions for children with disabilities)

It is important to consider the intellectual curiosity of students with intellectual disabilities, but this is not the only way to succeed in learning. Increasing students' interest in knowledge is the responsibility of all teachers, but the role of class teachers in a specialized school is invaluable.

The oligophrenopedagogue prepares students to actively comprehend their knowledge and actively solve cognitive problems. This is not an accident, but the logic

of the learning process. It is important to explain the nature of the acquisition of knowledge and the logic of the learning process, its essence. There are two concepts: the logic of the school subject and the logic of the educational process.

In the logic of the subject, the main ideas of science are reflected in the content of the curriculum. However, the logic of the subject does not determine the specific course of the educational process in the classroom, does not take into account the level of knowledge and intellectual maturity of students with intellectual disabilities. The successful use of various forms and methods to increase children's interest in knowledge and learning has become a habit in our schools today. At the same time, it is useful to take into account the fact that students with intellectual disabilities are able to independently apply their theoretical knowledge in the organization of educational work. For example, a geography teacher asked one of the students to make a visual material "Weather Vane", a device that determines the direction of the wind. To make such a learning tool, the student must have theoretical knowledge. To successfully complete the task, the student tries to study a particular subject more seriously, deepen knowledge, and interest in the subject increases.

The specific way of learning is determined by the logic of the learning process. According to the same logic of the educational process, both the acquisition of knowledge by schoolchildren and the development of cognitive activity are effective. In the logic of the educational process, such issues as how to explain cognitive tasks to students in order to understand what factual material to choose and to what extent, what types of independent work to take into account, what observations to make, and so on justified, evidence are resolved. All this is done to ensure that the learning process is effective in terms of the assimilation of knowledge by students and their intellectual development.

The correct logic of the learning process is such that the teacher implements the educational material in practice not as a rigid, unchanging process, but as a set of facts, specific ideas, concepts, generalizations and specific ideas. learn in the process of their own actions, which are included in the usual practice with skills.

Although the logic of the learning process is intertwined with the logic of the subject, they are not the same thing, the learning process is more dynamic. This is a broader concept that covers the logic of the subject and the psychology of students learning the material.

Thus, didactic scientists, taking into account the logic and mobility of the structure of the learning process, distinguish the main parts (stages of the learning process) in which the movement of auxiliary students from ignorance to knowledge takes place, these are:

1. Encourage students to learn and set practical problems to keep them interested and affect their emotions.
2. Creation of a problem situation.

3. Use the previous experience of mentally retarded children in the educational process.
4. Students' perception of new material.
5. Understand the perceived material, formulate scientific concepts, master the rules.
6. Consolidate and improve the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired at school.
7. Apply knowledge, skills and competencies in practice.
8. Analyze learning outcomes, test the knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies of students.

It is important to take into account the child's interest in learning, but this is not the only way to successfully learn. It is also important to instill in children a sense of responsibility and responsibility for academic work. Elements of coercion include detaining a child after school and completing a task that he or she did not complete. However, the quality of education cannot be improved if children do not have the desire and interest to learn. Involve students in clubs. Classes strengthen and deepen the theoretical knowledge of students in the classroom. Depending on students' interest in a particular subject, they may consciously approach other subjects and learn the basics of science. For example, if a child may be interested in science, he may be interested in geography and history.

It is important that students are active in the classroom. But this does not happen spontaneously, it must be brought up by the teacher.

Thus, modern didactics has developed a whole system of ways to activate the learning process. For example, the setting of educational tasks in the learning process forms the desire for students to actively participate in acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities to master the material of the subject program.

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STANDARD LOADING IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND PUBLIC SPORTS AND HEALTH ACTIVITIES

Mukhammetov Ahmad

Senior Lecturer, Tashkent Financial Institute

Annotation

In the practice of educational institutions, in most cases, insufficient attention is paid to the independent involvement of students in physical education and mass sports, there are no clubs that suit their interests, classes are conducted on the basis of the same program for all. Therefore, in these exercises there is no attention to the definition of loads and their coordination in the body of the trainees. Students' interests are not taken into account and student initiatives are not supported. This, in turn, reduces students' interest in physical education and mass sports. As a result, students become inactive, and as a result of inactivity they develop various diseases in the body, immunity is reduced, students do not have information about physical activity. This article discusses the importance of load balancing in physical education and mass sports.

Keywords: physical culture, sports, physical education, physical development, physical training, physical training, students, standardization, sports training, exercises.

Introduction

The modern way of life requires radical renewal and development of the education and training system of reforms in the socio-economic, political, spiritual and cultural spheres. Therefore, one of the priorities of our state is to bring up the younger generation as active, well-rounded, highly spiritual, mature people who take an active part in the life of society through the development of the education system at the level of modern requirements and experience. [1]

School curricula in all subjects have changed, taking into account the demands of the times, including physical education, with high demands on students. In order to meet the requirements of this program, students are engaged in educational work at school and at home to gain knowledge. [2] Of course, to do such a great mental load work, you need to be energetic and physically fit. It is no secret that a healthy child performs all tasks with high quality, he is strong-willed, aspiring, curious. [3]

One of the most invaluable medications is exercise. Abu Ali Ibn Sina was the first to state scientifically that "a person who regularly engages in physical training will no longer need medicine."

The "health" of the population depends on many factors. In the period of economic policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, first of all, it is necessary to scientifically

substantiate the structure of the system of physical education, taking into account the climatic conditions and ethnic conditions of the republic.

On the other hand, the main factor of "health" is physical training. The practitioner has extensive experience in this matter. They are aimed at improving the results of various exercises, the formation of motor skills and abilities, increasing motor activity, improving the quality of teaching movement techniques and cultivating the qualities of physical movement.

The development of scientific and theoretical bases of physical activity in the process of physical education and mass sports, theoretical and practical and recommendations on the use of physical activity in the process of physical education and mass sports are relevant for today's professionals.

The effectiveness of physical education training depends in many ways on the normalization of the physical loads used in training. Proper use of loads in the process of physical education and sports contributes to the growth of physical development, physical training and sports results. In sports, especially high-performance sports, a great deal of attention is paid to the regulation of loads in professional sports. In the practice of physical education and mass sports, in most cases, this is not given enough attention. [4]

Load normalization is a specific diagnosis of physical education and mass sports. [5] Therefore, the physical fitness of students was studied and analyzed, taking into account the physical fitness, physical development, body constitution, health status, sports experience, physical education and personal interest in sports, taking into account the effectiveness of training methods . Alpomish and Barchinoy health tests were used.

From the first years of independence, our country has paid great attention to ensuring high sports results, developing professional sports, raising the sports status of Uzbekistan in the world arena. Currently, Uzbek athletes have a strong position in the world arena in such sports as boxing, wrestling, athletics, weightlifting, oriental wrestling. This is due, first of all, to the conditions created in the country for the development of physical culture and sports, modern sports facilities, sports infrastructure, organization and management of sports economy, innovation in the organization and management of physical culture and sports organizations, entrepreneurship, investment and innovation in sports. secondly, the sharp increase in the number of people interested in sports, the orientation of parents to sports, the skills of coaches, the development of physical culture and sports in educational institutions, the strengthening of physical culture and sports promotion are becoming increasingly important.

Involvement of students in active and regular participation in mass sports in higher education institutions is an important, integral part of the process of training highly educated professionals and their comprehensive development. After all, in addition to

strengthening health, sports also form in a person the character, will, ability to overcome difficulties. To this end, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 3, 2017 No 3031 "On measures for further development of physical culture and mass sports in Uzbekistan" is aimed at the mass development of sports Resolution No. 864 of October 20, 2018 "On measures to further improve the system of continuous sports competitions aimed at attracting students to sports" Physical training for students of secondary schools, academic lyceums, vocational colleges and higher education institutions and the continuity of sports competitions in a system of continuing education based on the national model of training and in accordance with its requirements.

The national values of our people in the field of physical culture, the spiritual heritage have served for centuries as a powerful source of spirituality for the peoples of the East. For many years, despite the totalitarian regime, the cultural values and traditions of the Uzbek people in the field of physical culture have been preserved. From the first years of independence, the physical education of the younger generation, the study of our invaluable national and cultural heritage created by our ancestors in strengthening their health has been one of the important priorities of state policy.

In the theory and methodology of physical education, special attention is paid to the normalization of physical activity. It states that the loads are appropriate for the age, gender, and physical fitness of the students. Researchers have also shown that light exercise does not benefit the body and that heavy exercise harms the body. [6,7]

But in the study process, the research, as noted, was conducted in the process of sports activities associated with high results. According to them, the highest, highest, closest, average and lowest levels of loading are listed. Functional indicators of the organism, such as respiration, heart rate, external signs of fatigue, play a special role in the transfer of loads. Heart rate is a key indicator when delivering loads. In a non-exerciser, the heart rate is 72 beats at rest, while this figure increases and changes as a result of exercise. Therefore, expert researchers have shown that exercise with a heart rate of less than 140 beats is of little benefit to the body (L.E. Lyubomirsky, T. Khayitov, 2017). Heart rate was found to be up to 170 beats during health-related physical activity, as well as at moderate levels of physical activity. As a result of high-intensity exercise, the heart rate has increased from 2020 to 240 beats, according to scientific sources.

In the practice of educational institutions, in most cases, insufficient attention is paid to the independent involvement of students in physical education and mass sports, there are no clubs that suit their interests, classes are conducted on the basis of the same program for all. Therefore, in these classes there is no attention to the definition of loads and their coordination in the body of the trainees. In this case, the interests of students are not taken into account, student initiatives are not supported. This, in turn, reduces students' interest in physical education and mass sports. As a result,

students become inactive, and as a result of inactivity they develop various diseases in the body, immunity is reduced, students do not have information about physical activity.

Based on the above ideas, the relevance of the research topic can be justified by the following.

First, physical activity is not taken into account in mass physical education and sports-health training. This leads to a low level of independent involvement of students in physical education and mass sports in their spare time, or to a lack of exercise as a result of overload. This raises the need for scientific substantiation and analysis of physical loads in physical education classes with students.

Second, today in the theory and methodology of physical education, the main focus is on maintaining and strengthening the health of the population. Creating a harmoniously developed generation requires a scientific and systematic approach to substantiating the role and importance of physical education and sports in the development of their health, consciousness and thinking in terms of medical, biological and socio-pedagogical features of the human body.

Thirdly, the reforms being carried out in our country to form a harmoniously developed generation should be carried out on the basis of modern conditions created for physical culture and mass sports, taking into account the personal interest of each student in physical culture and mass sports. , it is important to plan.

In our country, some aspects of physical education of the population, especially students, their involvement in mass sports are being studied as an independent topic, in a scientific-theoretical and fundamental way, to a certain extent.

During the past years of independence, the socio-political, economic and spiritual development of society, taking into account the human factor, its free and comprehensive development as an object and subject, including physical development, is reflected in a number of decrees and resolutions of the President. found.

At all stages of human development, the issues of physical education and physical maturity have been at the forefront of the experience of social life. The role of mass physical education in maintaining and strengthening human health, the scientific and methodological correct use of its results have been given special attention by researchers. Also, R.Khalmukhamedov, R. Matkarimov, T.Usmanhojaev, R.Salomov, A. Sadikov, M.Umarov, J.Umarov and other modern pedagogues.

However, these studies have not studied the goals and objectives related to the regulation of physical activity in the process of physical education and mass sports, and little attention has been paid to the issues of mass physical education of students, their involvement in mass sports and exercise.

Leading specialists of the Republic of Uzbekistan, prominent foreign experienced teachers, many scientists (A.Novikov, L.Matvieev, V.Filin, G.Sh. .Bogdanov,

A.Gujalovskiy, L.Lyubomirskiy, V.Volkov, B.Prokudin, M.Zatsiorskiy, V.K.Balsevich, Yu.V.Verkhoshanskiy, A.A.Gujalovskiy, F.A.Kerimov, Sh.X .Khankeldiev, R.Salamov, T.S.Usmonkhodjaev, R.Khalmuhamedov, M.Umarov, K.D.Yarashev, A.K.Eshtaev and others) theoretically and practically studied. [8, 9, 10, 11.]

The use of scientifically and methodologically based physical activity in the process of independent participation of students in physical education and mass sports in higher education institutions increases the effectiveness of physical education, improves student health, ensures the body's adaptation to large physical loads, focuses on productivity and physical maturity.

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COMMUNICATIVE EXERCISES IN TEACHING GRAMMAR CHARACTERISTICS OF ENGLISH VERBS

Shakhlo Khakimovna Kharatova

Associate Professor of Tashkent State Transport University

Annotation

In this article, the principles of designing communicative-integrative exercises on teaching English verb and its grammatical features are explored at the level of higher education system students with English language specialty. The research was held by the author by making contrastive analysis of English and Uzbek Verb systems and finding out the field of interferences. While designing the system of exercises, a special attention was paid at the interference cases, the principles of systematic and communicative approach to the creation of exercises.

Keywords: Methodology, interference, competence, contrastive analysis, typology of exercises, systematic principle, CEFR levels.

Introduction

The main goal of today's methodology is the formation of communicative competence in students in the process of teaching foreign languages. Communicative competence, in turn, includes several sub-competencies, the first of which is linguistic competence. Linguistic competence means that a student has excellent knowledge and skills in English grammar and vocabulary. To do this, it is necessary to make a comparative analysis of the native language and a particular language unit in the target language, and to consider cases of interference depending on the results of the analysis. By linguistic interference we mean the errors made by a speaker of a second language as a result of the influence of one language on another. Once these situations are identified, the teacher should create a set of exercises to help students overcome these problems. In creating a set of exercises, it is advisable to move from the pre-communicative exercises to the basic (communicative) exercises, which serve the systematic principle, that is, from light to complex, and the formation of communicative competence. In our study, the main goal was to create a set of exercises for first-year students majoring in English to teach the grammatical features of the English verb phrase, and this article presents the main results of the study.

In order to teach any foreign language effectively, first of all, it is necessary to compare the native language of the students and the language they are learning, to make a comparative analysis of them. By comparing languages, the similarities and differences of these languages are revealed: while similarities make it easier to learn a second language, different features make learning a language more difficult, and these difficulties in turn lead to speech errors. will come. For example, in oral speech, some

students may pause or mispronounce. The Department of Linguistics, which deals with the identification of similarities and differences between two languages by comparing them with each other in foreign language teaching, is called Contrastive Linguistics. According to V. B. Kashkin, a Russian scholar, two branches of linguistics, comparative (comparative) and comparative (contrastive) linguistics, deal with the comparison of languages. Comparative linguistics studies the stages of historical development, differences and commonalities of related languages by comparing them. Comparative linguistics, on the other hand, compares any two languages in the world, and the languages may not be related. For example, comparative linguistics is important in studying the similarities and differences between the phonetic, morphological, or syntactic units of English and Uzbek, Russian and German, Turkish, and Chinese. By linguistic interference we mean the errors made by a speaker of a second language as a result of the influence of one language on another. It is natural for students to make mistakes when learning a language. "Mistakes are not a disease, but a sign that the distinctive features of the two languages in the mind of the student are incompatible and make it difficult for him to learn the language," says Yarseva. Interference cases, according to the results of observations, are often made by most students in certain linguistic situations, i.e., students repeat the same mistakes as each other. From this it is clear that these errors are caused not by individual factors of students, but by systemic language factors.

- The learning process is focused on speaking activities: developing the ability to communicate through listening, speaking, reading and writing;
- Linking exercise to different life situations;
- Use of communicative exercises (information gap, jigsaw, debate, interviews);
- Individualization of education, ie taking into account the individual learning abilities and characteristics of each student.

Today, two types of grammar are distinguished: linguistic and pedagogical. Linguistic grammar is a set of language units, grammatical structures and rules of a language. Pedagogical grammar is a variant of linguistic grammar adapted to the age, level of knowledge and mother tongue of students. This concept was first introduced by N. Chomsky, who argued that the structure, expression and interpretation of grammatical rules should be changed and adapted based on the individual characteristics of students (age, mother tongue, profession). For example, the Perfect category of the English verb does not exist in the Uzbek verb. But for the Uzbek audience, the modern structure of the "auxiliary verb to be a friend" can be explained in the same way as in the Present Perfect tense:

In the communicative style, grammatical units are explained in a specific communication process, through some context, and the resulting grammatical units are reinforced through communicative exercises. Let's compare the sequence of

presenting the correct and incorrect verbs of the past tense in the traditional and communicative way:

The Traditional Way.

1. The teacher teaches two pronunciation variants of the “ed” form;
2. In some cases, if the last letter of a verb ends in a consonant "d", it explains the hesitation (wed- wedded);
3. Students are given a table of incorrect verbs to read;
4. The pronunciation of incorrect verbs is taught in mechanical drills and students are asked to memorize them.

Communicative Method.

1. Divide students into two groups and give them two texts (about recent events) and familiarize them with the texts;
2. Ask them to find the verbs in the text that end in “ed” and explain that they are correct verbs. Then we give the example of the past tense of other correct verbs and explain the rules of pronunciation and hesitation;
3. Distinguish and explain the wrong verbs in the text;
4. Have students read the text again and discuss what they did not understand;

In conversation, students are asked to use the verb forms they have been taught. In order to know the level of teaching verbs in first-year Uzbek classrooms, it is necessary to analyze the curriculum for grammar. However, first of all, it is worth considering that different Methodists have analyzed the coverage of the topic, a set of exercises and assessment methods in the textbooks, namely in grammar textbooks. For example, Galskova.N. and Gez.N. They say that when choosing grammar based on a communicative approach, they should do the following when choosing sources of learning:

1. When choosing materials, they should include examples of natural language used in various communication processes, it is not necessary to use fictional, artificial examples;
2. Grammar rules should be presented in sufficient quantity to suit students' comprehension;
3. In the strengthening part of the lesson it is necessary to carry out interactive, active exercises among students, it is expedient to work in pairs, in groups.

Teaching Topics, New Grammar Rules Consists of 3 Stages:

- Introduction to grammatical units or rules;
- Initial strengthening;

- Work on developing the ability to use grammatical concepts in oral and written speech.

A set of exercises is important in learning any aspect of language. Exercises are a key factor in acquiring and consolidating new knowledge. For this reason, it is important to organize the exercises properly, based on the goals and objectives of the lesson and in order to increase the effectiveness of the learning resources.

CONCLUSION

Today, the main focus in foreign language teaching is on the formation of communicative competence in language learners. As a result, it is advisable to teach grammatical units and rules not in the traditional way, but based on a communicative approach. The exercise prepared for the study consisted of a set of exercises called pre-communicative and communicative exercises, which were arranged in a sequence from easy to difficult, from the structure of the grammatical unit to the rules of its use and in which cases the speaker used it in communication. The researcher based his set of exercises on the following factors:

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INFLUENCE OF VARIOUS CHILD-PARENT RELATIONSHIPS ON THE EMOTIONAL SPHERE OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Abibullayeva Perdegul Ongarbaevna,

Trainee teacher at Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz

Abstract

The article discusses various aspects of a child's life in the family, and we can conclude how difficult it is to create ideal conditions in which individual characteristics of a developing preschool child's personality will be taken into account. Because for the normal existence of a child, a mentally healthy child-parent relationship based on love and trust is necessary.

Keywords: Social and emotional stages of development, controlling of emotion, style of upbringing, social adaptation of preschool children.

Introduction

Although it is much easier to determine a child's physical growth, it is also necessary to determine the social and emotional stages of development. The role of the social and emotional sphere of a preschool child is very important in the life of every child. This acts as a basic foundation in their lives as they grow. This foundation helps the child cope with their personal feelings, understand the feelings of others, respect other people's thoughts, and establish positive interactions with others.

In a situation of emotional anticipation of the possible consequences of their behavior, the preschooler considers in advance whether they are going to act well or badly. Having assessed how much a possible action corresponds to generally accepted norms and, in case of a negative outcome, the child develops a state of anxiety that can slow down wrong actions [1].

The relationship between the child and the parent is also important for what kind of person the child will be, as it will help shape the nature of the future relationship. Nature versus nurture is a key component of a child's personality development. How a child is raised contributes a lot to shaping who they become in addition to their genes. Recent trends in studies of twins raised in the same families and different families have shown that about 66 percent of personality variation is due to genetic exposure (Bouchard, 1994). On the other hand, some studies argue that it is still unknown whether genes have much control over personality, and that genes must be considered at the cellular level to influence personality (Kraus, 2013).

Emotional learning begins at a young age, and develops as you get older. Infants express their feelings through nonverbal communication and depend on their parents to recognize their cues. Emotional expression is closely related to both the social and cultural influences of family and environment. A child's relationship with his or her

parents gives him or her the opportunity to express both positive and negative emotions in a socially and culturally acceptable way.

When a child is four years old, he begins to realize his individuality. He or she is interested in physical activity and will strive to develop his or her motor skills and reasoning abilities. This helps him to achieve a good level of confidence and be proud of himself. At this age, parents need to help their child:

- Distinguish between good and bad behavior.
- Organize opportunities for communication with other children.
- Promote understanding of other people's feelings; *встрь других людей*;
- Use creative, role-playing, and competitive games with other children.
- Assist in monitoring the implementation of various instructions and rules.

First, it is important to remember that each child's development is unique and complex. There may be small or huge differences in a child's social and emotional development, as this is due to a number of factors. Second, many factors influence how children express their social and emotional competencies. For example: there are some similarities between the emotional development of parents and children as a result of hereditary factors.

American psychologist John Watson said that children learn through the process of learning. The experiment was conducted on a nine-month-old baby who was shown a rat, and there was a lot of noise in the background. Later, it was noticed that the child started crying just by looking at the rat. Similarly, if there is an expression of physical love in the family, the child also expresses their love through contact, kisses, or hugs. Family relationships and how they express their emotions affect a child's emotional development. If parents are stable in their behavior and express their feelings in a balanced way, then their children will follow in their footsteps. If parents are prone to violence, then children also reproduce aggressive behavior. If children are overly indulged, chances are that they will become undisciplined and stubborn. On the contrary, if parents don't show any affection, they become introverted and submissive. Like the family, society also affects the emotional development of the child. If the environment is emotionally charged, the child becomes emotionally unstable. If people are stable and in control of their emotions, the child remains so too. They learn to control their emotions and try to conform to socially acceptable behaviors.

Emotional management is essential for healthy physical and mental health. When a child is emotionally charged, several changes occur in the body, such as changes in pulse rate, blood circulation, eye stretching, effects on the digestive system, and much more.

An emotional view of development allows the child to understand or control their inner emotions. The social aspect of development helps balance external elements, such as interaction with family and friends.

Many researchers study the ways in which responsiveness and demanding behavior interact to form a general psychological climate in the family. Using this approach, the experts identified four main parenting styles that usually appear in preschool age: authoritative, authoritarian, condescending and detached. Although no parent is completely consistent in different situations, over time, parents seem to follow some general trends in their approach to parenting. Based on this, it is possible to describe the relationship between parents and children in terms of the prevailing parenting style. These descriptions can be used to provide guidance to professionals and parents interested in understanding how variations in the parent-child relationship affect child development.

- Authoritative parents are both responsive and demanding, they are firm, but they discipline with love and affection, not force. These parents explain the rules and expectations to their children instead of just stating them.
- Authoritarian parents are also very demanding, but less responsive. They tend to be highly disciplined, often relying on physical punishment and abandonment of affection to shape their child's behavior.
- Condescending parents are responsive, but not particularly demanding; they expect little from their children and discipline them little.
- Separated parents are not responsive or demanding. They may be careless or unaware of the child's need for love and discipline.

What makes a parent more likely to use one style as opposed to another? Ultimately, the parenting style that a parent uses is shaped by many factors: the parent's developmental history, education and personality, the child's behavior, and the immediate and broader context of family life.

Thus, the parent's behavior toward the child is influenced by factors such as work, marriage, family finances, and other factors that can affect the parent's behavior and psychological well-being. In addition, a systematic comparison of parenting methods in families living in different settings shows that parents belonging to different cultures, different social classes, and different ethnic groups raise their children differently.

However, research has shown that aspects of children's behavior and psychological development are related to the parenting style they were raised with. Thus, preschoolers with authoritative parents tend to be curious about new situations, focused and able to play, confident, in control, and fun. Children who are usually treated authoritatively tend to be moody, unhappy, fearful, withdrawn, irresponsible, and irritable. Children of condescending parents tend to have low social responsibility and independence, but they are usually more cheerful than the conflicted and irritable children of authoritarian parents. Finally, children whose parents are separated tend to have a higher proportion of psychological difficulties than other adolescents.

Current research conducted over the past 30 years' points to two overarching aspects of the parent-child relationship that appear to be systematically linked to a child's psychological development: how responsive parents are and how demanding they are. Responsive parents treat their children warmly and with understanding, enjoy them and try to look at things from their point of view. Unlike parents, who have low sensitivity, they tend to be aloof, dismissive, or critical. They show little pleasure in interacting with their children and are often insensitive to their emotional needs. Demanding parents maintain consistent standards of behavior for their child. In contrast, parents who are not demanding enough are too lenient; they exercise minimal control, give little guidance, and often give in to their child's demands. Healthy psychological development of children is facilitated when parents are both responsive and moderately demanding.

At preschool age, children often begin to assert the desire for autonomy, challenging their parents. Sometimes a child's newfound self-confidence during a serious task can jeopardize the parent-child relationship. It is important that parents recognize that this behavior is normal for a preschooler. Healthy development of independence is facilitated by parent-child relationships that provide support and structure for developing a child's sense of autonomy.

Numerous studies have examined the impact on child development of factors such as divorce, remarriage, and employment of parents (especially mothers). As a rule, these studies show that the quality of child-parent relationships has a more important impact on the child's psychological development than changes in the structure or composition of the family.

Simply put, parenting that is responsive and demanding is associated with healthier child development, regardless of the parent's marital status or employment. However, if changes in the parents' marital status or work life disrupt the parent-child relationship, short-term consequences for the child's behavior can be expected. One of the goals of professionals working with families under stress is to help them restore healthy patterns of parent-child interaction.

To build a healthy parent-child relationship, parents can do several things to help build positive relationships and prevent aggressive or anxious behavior from occurring.

- Parents should communicate with their children, encouraging them to express their emotions and share their needs.
- Parents must provide for their children by meeting their physical and emotional needs.
- Parents should ensure consistent discipline by setting healthy boundaries and making sure that children follow them.

Also, it should be noted that for the comprehensive emotional development of a preschooler, parents need to ensure constant dynamics of various actions. The brain

of a preschooler should be subject to stress and active training, since at this age the child is characterized by an emotional deficit that generates boredom, melancholy, and apathetic mood. It is necessary to include the child in both positive and negative situations that arise in the family. At the same time, it is necessary to prepare the preschooler in advance for the perception of such situations (divorce, death of relatives, etc.), since when faced with life problems, the child develops endurance and balance, empathy.

Physical, social, and mental activity can improve a child's social and emotional perception and make them feel more involved in their family. Family rituals also promote a sense of belonging. Bedtime routines are associated with better sleep patterns among children. Family treatments can also make it easier for children to deal with stress, such as separation from their parents or divorce.

On the other hand, the child, with the help of the adults around him and the influence of culture in general, learns the feelings accepted in this society, in particular, becomes attached to feelings of friendship, love, gratitude, patriotism and other high feelings. It is thanks to family relationships that children develop the development of concentration and will, boys learn the role of a man and lay the foundations for the future role of a father, girls learn female roles, learn the values of being a wife and mother, and master the skills necessary for this.

In the conditions of the family educational process, the child learns various mechanisms that contribute to the social adaptation of the preschool child and gain experience in interpersonal relationships. Psychologists have proposed three types of mechanisms.

Reinforcement, which is characterized by the formation of a moral-value type of behavior in a preschooler. The child learns the basic rules of behavior, understands the meaning of the concepts of "good" or "bad". It should be noted that the child learns the rules without completely copying the established principles of the family. The preschool child transforms them through the prism of personal experience, creating their own "code of rules" of behavior and interpersonal communication, implementing it in their activities (forming amoral skill) [3].

Identification is characterized by the child's imitation of the emotional reactions of significant authoritative adults, thus focusing on the example of their behavior in various situations. At the same time, one should not shift responsibility to upbringing by way of a spontaneous example (sample), since the child may not always be present at the moments of manifestation of socially significant and positive reactions of parents. In this case, you can't count on effective identification.

Understanding is characterized in the cooperation of adults during the process of forming self-awareness and personal characteristics of the child. This mechanism is most effectively revealed in the process of family education, since parents are guided in the inner world of the child, anticipate the emotional reaction of the preschooler.

The importance of family influence and family ties is undeniable and obvious. Despite the interrelation of family, social and pedagogical education, which complement each other, they are not interchangeable and cannot become such.

Family education is the most emotional in nature than any other type of education, because "it is guided by parental love for children, which causes children to respond to their parents" [2].

The sense of belonging that people experience when they have good social relationships has a positive impact on their mental health. Children who have good social relationships have higher self-esteem than those who don't, and are less likely to experience mental health problems, including anxiety and fear. There is also evidence that prosocial behavior in childhood leads to improved psychological health in adulthood.

The social environment can also affect a child's health by influencing their parents' behavior. For example, one Australian study reported that parents who live in communities where services are more accessible are less likely to use hostile parenting methods (which are expected to have a negative psychological impact on their children) than those who live in communities where resources are not available.

A child's social environment is largely dictated by where his or her parents live and send them to school. In turn, the social environment largely determines with whom children form social relationships and the quality of these social relationships, since many of the relationships that children form is in their family or neighborhood. Thus, parents' decisions (or lack of decision-making authority) about where to live, work, and study can significantly affect their children's health and well-being.

The quality of child-parent relationships is affected by the parent's age, experience, self-confidence, and self-esteem. Parental self-confidence is an indicator of parental competence. Mothers who see themselves as effective parents are more competent than mothers who feel incompetent. In addition, mothers who consider themselves effective also tend to find their children less difficult to handle.

Thus, considering the various aspects of a child's life in the family, we can conclude how difficult it is to create ideal conditions in which the individual characteristics of the developing personality of a preschooler will be taken into account. Because for the normal existence of a child, a mentally healthy child-parent relationship based on love and trust is necessary.

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“DEVONU LUGATIT TURK”. HISTORICAL STUDY OF TURKISH LANGUAGES IN COMPARATIVE STUDY

Y. M. Ibragimov

Professor, Doctor of Philological Sciences NSPI

U. Y. Ibragimova

NSPI Department of Uzbek Language,
Candidate of Philological Sciences, Docent

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The great encyclopedist Makhmud Kashgari's "Devonu lugatit turk" is very valuable about the division of Turkic tribes and clans in the 11th century, their place of residence, customs, folklore, socio-economic status, history, commonalities and differences in language, reliable data are given.

“Devon” also has more than seven and a half thousand lexical units, of which more than five thousand words appear in the modern Uzbek language and its dialects in the form of exact or some semantic or phonetic changes in their meanings at that time. For example, many of the words in the first volume of “Devon” are used in the same sense as “Devon” in Uzbek literary language and dialects. *Et “gosht”* (1.70) meat in the Uzbek dialect of Kipchak; *am; iu em* in Oguz-type dialect; belly meat - thin meat sticking to the liver (1.70); Kipchak type dialects of the Uzbek dialects of the Southern Aral Sea. Work (KKRD, 201); ep “cure” (1.74), Uzbek dialects of the Southern Aral Sea kipch *em* “cure”; *esh “companion”, “comrade* (1.74)”, Uzbek dialects of the Southern Aral Sea in the same sense.

Mahmud Kashkari refers to a large group of dialects (literary language based on the leading dialects) as "Turk" a specific dialect, tribe with their names (including *bechenek, qifchaq, oguz, yemek, bashgirt, yabaqu, tatar, yagma, Uyghur, Chinese, Chigel, Tuxsi, Tangut*) and others. From time to time, their differences from the leading dialects "Turkish", their peculiarities, their location are noted.

In classifying the Turkic languages, Mahmud Kashqari approaches them not in terms of kinship and closeness to each other as they do now, but in terms of the natural purity of the language, in terms of how much it is influenced by other languages. According to Mahmud Kashkari's scientific view, he accepts the Turkic related languages in his original state without distinguishing between them and groups them according to the extent to which the languages that are disrupting their natural state with the words they have learned are failing. There is a good reason why the author repeatedly says “pure language is pure language”. It should be noted that the scholar called *Kyrgyz, Kipchak, Oguz, Tuxsi, Yagma, Chigil, Igroq, Yaruq* languages "pure Turkic language".

Indeed, the “Devonu lugatit turk”’s embodies the phonetic, morphological and lexical-semantic features of the languages of the 11th century Turkic peoples, from which each of the modern Turkic peoples finds information on the history, dialects, formation, development, stages of development, ethnogenesis, history of statehood takes. For example, in “Devon” *mγ* the word *tu* is interpreted as “*soch*”, “*tuk*”, “*qil*”. Then, in the Uzbek folk dialects of the Jaunbiy Aral Sea *мүк*, *мүбум* are synonymous words and *tu* is the *mγ* basis for both. The word *tugin* in Uzbek dialects is based on the word *tuk*. If we take into account the fact that in the dictionaries of the XI century the word *mγ*, “*tuk*” was used in the sense of “*soch*”, “*qil*”, it becomes clear that the combinations of *chachin чачын йулды-жулды*, *түгин qaldyrmady* are historically synonymous parallels.

“Devon” has connections like *уш түкеди*. The verb *түке* (*di*) in the cut function is preserved in our literary language as part of the word complete. Thus, the initial (meaning changed) base of the word *tugal* (*tuga*, *tuke*, the sound of the consonant “**k**” between two vowels) is formed from the suffix “**I**”. Therefore, a verb is formed from a word that has become a suffix by a special suffix: *tuga + l + la-tugalla*. The complete word in Uzbek dialects of the Southern Aral Sea is *түкуш*: *дүкүш*:*дүгүш* - toy, the collision of rams with each other or the collision of something with each other turns out to be related to the verb. That's the word. *түкәл*, *түкәллә*, *йл*, *қпчти*. *түвәл*; *түвәллә*, *джл*, *қпчти*. *Түвәллә*

In Uzbek dialects of the Southern Aral Sea a knife and a saw are used to cut something. In “Devon” the words *бычды* “cut”, *бычылды* “cut off”, *бычма* “harvested land”, *бычғу* “arracha” are used. The words “cooking”, “cooked” and *бышды*, *бышығ* are recorded. Thus, in the 11th century Turkic languages, when the sounds **sh** and **ch** differed in their meanings as phonemes, “... made two different words: one meaning “cut” (with the phoneme **ch**) and the other” *pishmoq* “(with the phoneme **sh**). [2.185]. The first base “**bych**” is preserved in Uzbek dialects of the Southern Aral Sea in the words *pichti*, *pichtirdi*, *pyshqy* “arracha” and the verb *pichirlatty* can be said to be derived from this base.

If every word interpreted in Mahmud Kashgari's “Devon” is common to all the Turkic languages of that period, then there is no mention of which language the word belongs to. If the word being interpreted does not apply equally to all the Turkic languages of that period, but only to a specific language or appearance of a certain language or a certain category of language, then it is stated and explained to which nation it belongs. For example, *ол үүкүнч етти-у* he prayed seven times (in Oghuz). Even now the verb *yukunmaq* is pronounced in Uzbek dialects of the Southern Aral Sea’s oguz tip (oghuz) and yelashan kipchak type shevas. In the Kipchak type dialects *jugundi*, *tabyndy* is used in the sense of “to worship”, “to obey”, “to worship”; in the modern Kazakh and Karakalpak languages, it is preserved in the form of a *жүгүнди*, *табынды* in the same sense as in “Devon” [3.125].

For example, the word *улыч* is used to pamper and kiss children *улычым*; oghuz, *улым* quoted; oghuz, kipchak *ulyt*, pine: *улым:қарағым:чырағым* Kipchak in “Devon” *иңир “кеч”*, twilight “late”, “time of sunset”; Oghuz *imir* “district” words kipchak twilight “early and late sunlight”; oghuz *imir* “district”, the owner-Kipchak “smoke”; Sometimes the words shown as belonging to another language are also. The word tunak ‘*zindon*’, ‘*qaras*’ (balasagun) (1,387) occurs in the Uzbek language and its dialects with a difference in meaning such as *түнәк: түнек: таш түнәк ‘қароңғи’, ‘тош қоранғи’*. For example, DLT. *ashaq* “bottom”, “lower” (I, 97) - ogztsh. *ashaq* in that sense: DLT. *әкин* (sowing) “crop”, “arable land” (I, 107) -ozztsh *әкин*, sowing, qpchtd. *iegin / yegin*; DLT. *қарынчақ* ventricular “ant” (I, 400) - *қарынжа*, digestion. *qarynja*, qptshd. ants; DLT. select “sparrow” (DLT. III, 238) -ogztd. *sechə*, qpchtd. *chumchuq*; DLT. *örken* “qayysh” (I, 132) –ogztd., qpchtd. “Rope”; DLT cotton “fluffy”, “cotton” (I, 300); -ogztd., qpchtd. cotton; down, “loose”, “soft”, “cotton separated from seeds”; DLT. “so” (I, 137) -qpchtd. “possess”, “protect”, “forgive”; DLT. *taquq* “chicken” (II, 330); -ogztd., qpchtd. chicken; DLT. *uzluq*: ogil “*molxona*” (I, 124) –ogztd. *ағыл*, qpchtd. *қора: малқора:малхана*; DLT. The word *benek* “grain”, “seed” (I, 367), which is characteristic of the language of argucha argu and similar categories, is a literary Uzbek word *дәнәк*, grain ogztd. *беджәнәк*; qpchtd, is recorded in the form *мүжәнәк/мүжәнәк/мүжәнә*.

Mahmud Kashgari emphasizes that if some words are in a certain form in one dialect and another word is used in its place in another dialect. For example, when other Turks called a bowl, a bowl, a bowl a foot, the Oguzs used the word *djanaq* (chanak) instead (I, 112) - oguz. *йл.kipch. чанақ*; bowl; jl qpchtd. *айақ/чанақ*, foot / pelvis, in the speech of some villagers, under the influence of Karakalpak, Kazakh dialects, the lexeme *tostagan* serves as a synonym for the word foot. In some Turks weave every *өрүң*, white color, the Oguzs say *aq // aq//* (I, 153); some Turks called it “wine”, “musallas”, “maini” -suchik and the inhabitants of the Ila valley (*yagmo*, *tuxsi*, *chigil*) called *maini kyzyl sochik* (I.387) -ad.orf. *chuchuk* “sweet”; *үызтш. süçik* “sweetness”, “sweet”, “sweet”, “delicious” qpchtd. “Tuchchy / chüchchi”; red sweet “wine”, “mai”.

Among the lexical layers from “Devon”, there are words that are used in one dialect in one sense and in another in another. In the Chigil Turks, the word *үлүш* means village, and Balasagün and the city of Argular above them mean city. (I, 94) - Uzbek dialects of the Southern Aral Sea’s, share “contribution”; in other Turks, a cow means “cow”; the Oghuzs called the female tortoise by this word (I, 135) - in the Bukhara and Northern Uzbek Oghuz dialects of the Uzbek language the cow *инәк* means “cow”; the other Turks called the kitchen *инәк ashlyk*, the Oguzs called wheat *ашлык* (I, 137) - Uzbek dialects of the Southern Aral Sea’s, *ashlyq* “grain”, “courage”; other Turks called worms “insects” worms, only Oguzs called wolves worms (I.328), now Turkmens call them worms. In most Turks, the word *чатылды* means “suvady”, *chapildi*, while in Uyghurs

it means to strike the neck (II, 135) - Uzbek dialects of the Southern Aral Sea's, *чанылды* "plastered", "cut".

There are also many words from Devon. Heard the word *chakdy* only in Oguz, the meaning of *aytdi* was also used: *ol sozug anka chakdy-u* heard the word in his ear *ол созуг аниң қулоққа чақды* (II, 24); DLT., bitten *соқты* "made" repaired".

Mahmud Kashgari has two different approaches to foreign words. There are all sorts of things about marriage that have been absorbed into life, but their names don't exist in our language. The scholar therefore approves of using them as in those neighboring languages. He thinks it is harmful to use words in another language instead of words in that language. "If we were based on the second opinion of M.Kashgari, instead of the Turkish words *билгә, бутук, урағым* we needed words such as Arabic scholar, book, woman" [4.67].

"Devon" also has many lexical units that are not listed as belonging to a particular Turkic language. Obviously, while a certain part of such words is related to the process of word acquisition, another part dates back to the period when the languages of the TB became the common language. The study of such words is important in determining the Turkic peoples, in particular, the issues of ethnogenesis, glotagenesis of the Uzbek people and the process of their formation, development and formation as a nation, which Turkic and non-Turkic tribes participated. In Devon, the word *chigit* (I.356) is said to belong to the Argu language. In modern Uzbek languages and dialects, as well as in the Karakalpak, Kazakh and Turkmen languages of the Southern Aral Sea, it is used in the sense of *chigit* / *чигит/шигит* due to the compatibility of **sh-ch**.

In Mahmud Kashgari's "Devon", too, the methods of using words in a figurative sense are diverse (DLT.1963). In the process of migration, the word has a new meaning based on its function - unity of meaning. For example, the word *in* is used in the language only in the sense of wild animals (lion, fox). He also has a demonic form (1.84). Then each word began to be applied to an animal bed. This word sounds like this in a folk saying; If the fox hits its own nest *тiлкy өз iнгa ypcа yзyз болyр*, it will become a fox. There is no doubt that the expansion of the meaning of the word *in* here began in a very ancient folk proverb.

Commenting on the word "lung", Mahmud Kashkari writes: "The lungs are white liver. The reason for this is that anger appears in the lungs. The use of this word in this sense is the origin of the word rather than its origin. Rain is called "heaven" (1.148). There are many examples of this in the modern Uzbek language and its dialects: I dropped a plate, I ate a plate, I read Abdulla - I read Abdulla Aripov's poems. The wooden "tree" (111.15). According to Mahmud Kashkari, the word *yigoch* is used in the language of the 11th century tribes in a slightly different way. The word at that time meant "tree", "measure of length", "wood". In the modern Uzbek literary language, the word "wood" is used instead of the first meaning, mainly in the Kipchak dialects of Uzbek dialects of the Southern Aral Sea.

In short. “Devonu lug'atit turk” is not only a linguistic work, but also an encyclopedia of its time, which contains valuable materials on the history, socio-economic situation, customs, geography, natural conditions, ethnography, dialectology and folklore of different peoples.

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DLT –Devonu lug'atit –it turk

KKRD - Karakalpak-Russian dictionary

kka. - Karakalpak language

kipchd. - Kipchak dialect

ogzd. - Oghuz dialect

ogztd. - Oghuz type dialects

kpchtd - Kipchak type dialects

yl - “Y” dialects

jl - “J” dialects

THE HISTORY OF THE EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURES IN THE ERA OF GLOBALIZATION

Abdullayeva Dilrabo Zubayevna

Independent researcher at the Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture

Abstarct

In World linguistics, anthroponymic units are the most ancient and common sort of onomastic units: the scientific-theoretical and practical study of names, surnames, patronymics, nicknames, and nicknames has always been a focus. In linguistics, anthroponymic units include not just a person's name, surname, patronymic, nickname, and nickname, but also their name, surname, patronymic, nickname, and nickname.

The name, patronymic, and surname have long been of significant interest to scientists as anthroponymic units, and they have been gathered, described, and analyzed in many ways. Nicknames and nicknames are extra names to a person's main name, and they are one of the less well-studied units of Uzbek anthroponymy. Anthroponyms, including pseudonyms, are distinguished from other onomastic units by the lack of their own autonomous, special language substance in terms of legalization. On the basis of dictionary units characteristic of the appellative level of the Uzbek language and other onomastic, more anthroponymic units, Uzbek nicknames and nicknames are developed.

The riches of the names of the onomastics of that language, the entire sum of the nouns with the patronymic, is made up of certain nicknames and nicknames in the language. The onomastic fund of the language distinguishes proverb nouns based on the property of the subject or object to which they refer. They are the names of many inanimate and live subjects' living beings or human beings. The so-called horses are classified into numerous large groups, according to these indicators. A vast number of them are made up of fictitious names given to persons. In the field of linguistics, they're known as anthroponyms.

Anthroponyms are divided into types in the genus Tuban in Special Studies: 1) nouns, 2) nicknames, 3) nicknames, 4) surnames, 5) potronomic names also include other forms and methods of naming a person .

A nickname is an Arabic word that refers to a name, a nickname, or a surname by which a person is mocked or ridiculed because of a characteristic.

It is well known that nicknames are given to people based on their personalities and qualities. As a result, they show what sort of seed or tribe people belong to, their physical inadequacies, their character, their method of speaking, any flaws in dressing,

or any changes in character, occupation, nationality, similar good and coughing qualities in people, and character-characteristics. For instance, anatomical abnormalities are denoted by nicknames in the human body.

Ch i n n o q. The original meaning of this lexeme is that the ear is cut off, the ear is kertic. It is used both in artistic style and in colloquial speech in the task of nicknames in relation to those whose ears are small and scarred.

A.Kahhor and S.Ahmed in his works used this nickname in relation to a kementician person in his ear, in order to achieve compactness in describing the portrait of the hero. For example: - Ch i n n o q came, - said a black guy who listened to the phone speaker and sat down and stood up to stretch out to a partner of a loose pawnshop.

-What did you say?

- Chinnoq, I want to say n o q came. Are you hearing me, what trouble, Nazir!?

Unless Ayam hadn't seen Dad's ear genticity for so many years, Juwon nicknamed him ch I n n o q, and they all laughed at the same time.

A. based on the preceding two examples.

S. Kahhor and Kahhor

The ch I n n o q lexeme is clearly employed in the role of nicknames in Ahmad Styles' literary work, both of which are anatomically deficient in the literary work, depicted in humor or very impactful.

In the Mangit dialect of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, such an ear was known as ch u r ri in comparison to the kementician ones.

Jumavoy ch he r r i's shopkeeper's child tractor opts.

B o q a q. In the lexieographic sources of the Uzbek language, the original meaning of this lexeme marks the disease as a consequence of a violation of the thyroid gland's function, the tumor meanings created as a result of damage to the enlarged gland, and the tree body as a result of this disease.

This word is also utilized in the task of nicknames in artistic works in order to achieve compactness while describing a portrait. For example, the imam and Khatib Abdurahman domla was the first mukhtaram of the same mosque, and the second was the mosque's muezzin, and the third was the muezzin of Samad b u q o q from the neighborhood's beautiful word chatter.

The nickname b o q o q was used in this context in regard to the person with the same disease and was used in the role of the nickname in reference to him.

The nickname s o q o q is used to refer to such people in the Republic of Karakalpakstan's Mangit dialect.

House of Karim s o q o q We're telling you about Galin Ta'ya.

Sorry for the inconvenience. The disorder that causes hair to fall out is known as baldness. This lexeme refers to the part of the head where the hair is shed, whether partially or entirely.

K A l is also used in the function of nicknames in relation to those who shed hair. For example: Asra K A L came from a heifer, a man of solid dexterity. An open yaktak who took over, a slave cowl in the hollow, tied to a bluish King choir, was a handsome young man who threw a holparan rumol on his shoulders.

This word is used in place of the word combinations that describe the shedding of hair in artistic works. As a result, the ixcham form creators utilized the nickname k a l to perfectly convey the outward comparison of persona. Nicknames are shown in an artistic work, which is a way of seeing numerous components of an image in a compact context in a deep meaningful and expressive way.

The konotative meanings of words are used to create nickname lexemes. It is divided into three categories by foreign linguists: portable meaning-forming tools, portable meaning-forming tools, and portable meaning-forming tools. In particular, the French linguist splits it into species such as metaphor, metonymy, and synecdocha in its linguistic lexicon.

E.Begmatov investigated nicknames and nicknames in the Uzbek language using anthroponymic units and covered their character-characteristics in a broad sense. Although A. Husanov investigated several nicknames among historical anthroponyms, nicknames in Uzbek linguistics were not specifically gathered and monographic research was not carried out.

In the past, the nickname suffix was used to denote a pseudonym. Nicknames and nicknames are an additional name for them, and they have affinity and commonality in this regard. Some innovators and artists were given nicknames as a result of their work. Such nicknames are called nicknames.

According to the meaning and motive of the nicknames in his candidate's dissertation, E.Begmatov divided them into ten groups. Rahimov divided the occurrence of nicknames in the language of Khorezm locals into five groups when investigating regional anthroponymy in Khorezm. In the Uzbek language, there have also been a lot of research on nicknames. They are A.Ishaev and R.Sapaev, both from M. Ashidova's pen.

Only in exceptional circumstances are nicknames used individually. In the majority of situations, a person chooses a name and has it written in a little letter. This instance casts doubt on the nicknames' noble origins.

Distinctive features of nicknames and nicknames

№	Features of nicknames	Features of nicknames
1	Nicknames are given to a person by others.	The nickname is chosen by the person himself.
2	Although nicknames are anthroponymic units, they are translated into another language, such as component.	Nicknames are not translated, they are transcribed as a name.
3	Nicknames sometimes rhyme to the original name.	Except for the nickname.
4	Nicknames exist only in oral language.	Nicknames are included in official documents together with the original name of the artists.
5	Nicknames are written in small letters, when they come before the name, big, when they come after the name.	Nicknames are always written with a capital letter, such as a name, surname, otatism.

Simple nicknames and nicknames play an important role in the anthroponymy of the Uzbek language. Structure, motivational-nominative, lexical foundation, historical-etymological source, technique of legalization, application of models, and all used to classify pseudoonyms. Nicknames are split into permanent and supplementary (seasonal) nicknames based on their use. Nicknames are permanent nicknames that poets and writers, among others, use from the beginning to the finish of their creative work.

In the study of onomastics and onomosiology in Uzbek linguistics, the study of nicknames, nicknames employed in the language of artistic works and dialects, is crucial. It is a method of portraying numerous features of images in a tight setting that is deeply relevant and striking.

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CLASSIFICATION OF COMPLEX VOCABULARY IN UZBEK LINGUISTICS

Madaminov Abdurakhman

Karakalpak State University named after Berdaq

Candidate of Philological Sciences of the Department of Uzbek Linguistics Docent

Abstract

Word combinations are nominative units, they differ from other nominative units in terms of structure, expression and syntactic function. So far, both in general science and in Turkic languages, word combinations have been theoretically analyzed in depth as a separate syntactic unit. But the structure of complex word combinations, the methods of syntactic communication and the issues of its connection are one of the controversial issues that have not found its solution in full. Even, at the initial stages, in Russian linguistics N. N. Prokopovich emphasized that " one of such important issues should be paid attention to the study of the issue of the volume and limit of word combinations, especially since its theoretical issues remain without adequate study, while emphasizing in due time that it is interested in the issue of word combinations." (1)

Due to this critical confusion, Turkish languages also began to pay special attention to this issue. As a result, a number of scientific studies on the word combinations of ot and verb were carried out. In particular, in Kazakh Linguistics M. Balakaev, T. Sayrambaevs, in the tatar language M. Zakiev, in the Azerbaijani language Yu. Saidov, Turkmen language E.A. Potseluevsky, K. Sariev, in the language of Karakalpak N.A.Baskakov, in Turkish A.N.Such scientists as Baskakov were widely covered in scientific research. (2;3;4;5;6;7;8;9)

N, who conducted preliminary studies in Turkology on complex word combinations.A. Baskakov, along with the opening of the main legacies of word combinations, paid special attention to their structure. It divides word combinations into two types as attributive-substantive and attributive-attributive, indicating the processes of their complicationality. Attributive-substantive divides complex word combinations into noun and verb word combinations. From this, 10 of the noun word combinations, 3 of the verb types of compound indicate the methods of compounding the total of attributive-substantive word combinations in 13 ways. He also determined that the attributive-attributive word combination consists of both noun and verb complex word combinations. In the composition of complex word combinations with such a predicate, it is also emphasized the presence of several simple word combinations with and without an object. It is said that it is impossible to give a complete model of complex word combinations, as shown in N.A. Baskakov's work on complex word combinations. (8; B.177) but until that time, in studies on Turkic languages, the volume and limit of complex vocabulary, the issues of building molds were covered in different degrees.

He conducted a special study on Complex Phrases T. Sayrambaev emphasized the morphological features of complex phrases in the Kazakh language of nouns and verbs,

as well as the agreed, adapted and controlled methods according to the methods of syntactic communication. noun phrases; Fe'l word combinations, however, show their complexity through vivid examples using compact and method of management. (4; B.11-19)

Professor NA Baskakov, who conducted a separate study on the historical and typological structure of Turkic languages, classifies phrases on the basis of the following three principles: 1) semantic; 2) morphological; 3) syntactic-functional (8; B.131-164) However, the common semantic and morphological principle in Turkic languages emphasizes that it does not fully reveal the nature of word combinations. Therefore, in his research, special attention is paid to the synthetic-functional principle (8; B.132-136). As a result, word combinations according to their synthetic-functional properties are: a) attributive-substantive (A.S); b) is divided into simple and complex phrases such as attributive-attributive (A.A). For example: the worst person in the Karakalpak language, the worst person in a well-read simple word combination; The formation of an attributive-substantive compound word compound is shown as a well-flowed puppy. Such a determinant is said to define some of the characteristics of a noun (noun, adjective, number, etc.) in the function of the dominant part of the subordinate clause of a compound word. It also shows the complexity of simple Vocabularies as a result of the syntactic connection of mixed Complex Vocabularies through the methods of adhesion and control: a large tree-a large fruit tree - a large fruit tree whose fruits are drowned- like a large tree whose fruits ripen and fall to the ground.

Professor N.A Baskakov, who conducted a separate research on the historical-typological structure of Turkic languages classifies word combinations according to the following three principles: 1) semantic; 2) morphological; 3) syntactic-functional (8; B.131-164) but the principle of semantics and morphology, which is common in Turkic languages, emphasizes that it can not fully reveal the nature of word combinations. Therefore, in his research, a special emphasis is placed on the synthetic-functional principle (8; B.132-136). As a result, according to the word combinations synthetic-functional properties: a) attributive-substantive (A.S); b) attributive-attributive (A.A) are separated into such simple and complex word combinations. For example: the most jaman adam from the simplest word combinations of the most jaman, jaqsi aqigan in the Karakalpak language; it is shown that such an attribute-substantive complex word combination as jaqsi aqigan bala is formed. It is said that the subordinate part of complex word combinations with such a predicate determines the characteristics of a sign of a noun (noun, adjective, number, etc.) in the task of the dominant part without a whole. Also, as a result of the introduction of compound complex word combinations into the syntactic connection through the methods of adjacency, management, it is shown that simple word combinations are complicated: a large tree-a large fruit tree – whose fruits are drowned, a large fruit tree - whose fruits are like a large tree, whose fruits are poured into the ground by drowning.

The above examples show that the subordinate part of the noun complex word combinations of the attributive-substantive character will consist of a determinative determinative compound in one case. And the identified part forms a substantive relationship that belongs to the noun group and is represented by such word categories as noun, adjective, number, pronoun. Attributive-holli or adverbial word combinations are also formed from determinative-determined parts, forming new Attributive-Holi or adverbial combinations that denote the sign of the sign. For example, like the child from the top nose, the top nose.

Complex word combinations with an attributive verb. For example: educating free-thinking young people; educating young people who are able to fluently express their own product of thought in oral and written forms, which in the future are free-thinking, we come across several simple word combinations that are mainly subordinated to the structure of complex word combinations with verbs, as well as the method of adjacency and management. But all of them, having entered into a subordinate connection with the upbringing (temperament) in the function of the word governor in the case of a whole, form a determinative-attributive relationship.

So, professor N. A. Baskakov, too, according to what category of independent words in the task of the dominant part of the word combinations are expressed, they are divided into two large groups, that is, combinations with nouns and verbs in a broad sense. Also, due to the syntactic function of the subordinate part, they are separated into attributive, substantive, adektiv, adverbial word combinations. Herein their meaning - relationship is also given special attention.

Taking into account the same aspects, his son A. N. Baskakov also classifies vocabulary in his work dedicated to "vocabulary in the current Turkish language". (9; B.13-15) it should be noted that word combinations as a nominative unit should be studied in the following two directions: a) structural-grammatic; b) functional-like semantic.

1. In the structural-grammatical direction, attention is given to the following two aspects: a) lexical - morphological aspect. Bunda is represented by various character-features, which refer to the combinations of ot and verb. Such noun and verb combinations combine with each other using different methods of syntactic communication. B) according to the syntactic attitude (equal and subordinate); is divided into several types, such as by the method of syntactic communication (cohesive, managerial, adaptive).

So, the definition of the composition of word combinations is determined not by the amount of all words involved in the composition, but by the function that these independent words perform in the composition of the combination. They are divided into simple and complex types in terms of structure. In this independent Word-Series perform the main task. And auxiliary words serve only to provide syntactic connections.

2. The functional-semantic principle is classified based on the lexical-semantic and syntactic properties of the part in which the sheep is identified. It is also shown that they consist of such types as substantive and attributive, and the accusative part, respectively, adektiv-adverbial. (9; B.13-15).

When classifying word combinations according to these characteristics, not only the amount of words in the composition of the combination, but also their semantic properties are taken into account. Therefore, in the classification of word combinations, word combinations consisting of words with three or more lexical meanings, but not semantically divided, having a completely different meaning and entering into a relationship with a dominant word as a whole, are considered simple combinations. For example: a tall guy, this spring of the year, like a man with a higher education. Such syntactic integrals are studied in Turkic languages, including Uzbek, as complex, semantically simple word combinations in terms of structure.

In addition, professor in Uzbek linguistics. A. Berdaliev in the methodological manual "syntax of word combinations in the Uzbek language" (1990-th year) divides word combinations into such types as simple, compound and complex according to how many syntactic connections exist in the composition. Therefore, it shows such combinations as apricot in the yard (adjacency), a good-natured pupil (adjacency), coming from school (management) as simple word combinations. (11; B.35) if there are combinations consisting of two or more syntactic links, such as flowering plums in the yard (prunes in the yard, flowering plums), then a joint or complex word will enter into the combinations. This situation is known as a chain of vocabulary in studies under study in the next period.(12)

1. Simple word combinations consisting of a single syntactic connection: the functional parts of simple word combinations are often indicated by the fact that the usual two independent words form a combination of consonants, possessive pronouns, pronouns and with the help of the word order or tone: love the motherland, my partner, talk over the phone, like to come quickly.

In the function of functional parts of such word combinations, words with a compound, paired, compound, as well as words with a portable meaning, can participate. First of all, they come in the composition of the subordinate part of the word combinations: diltar conversation; excellent quality material; work in winter-summer, like a conversation with the hero of Uzbekistan. Secondly, it comes to the task of the dominant part of the word combinations: to lay hands on the application; plowed cotton fields, winter fodder; to stick to the sheep in a nutshell; to sprinkle poison on his wife, etc. In the third, both parts of the word combinations come in the composition: to end the strike; to elect a full-fledged young-yalangs, to be a member of the youth organization byuro; to marry from the arrival of salt; to avoid disappointment, etc. Apart from these, one of the components of simple word combinations can also be in the character of a

joint word, another is a double word or a phraseological phrase: Take-run, stick to words, bake-bake bread-it's pits, like not thinking to draw a face to the ground.

2. In the composition of the compound word combinations, more than two meaningful words enter into a syntagmatic relationship: the handsome Caddy of Nadira; the eye-eyed silver flower of cherry. (H.Shams). In the composition of the above word combinations there are such words as Kaddi, flowers, which have an absolute dominant sign. Other words in the composition of the compound are combined with these words with the help of compatibility and bonding links, interpreted and conjugated them. The reason for the fact that such word combinations are called United is that the first of them is a pronoun, the pronoun is a pronoun, the pronoun is a pronoun; in the latter, the flowers of the Cherry, the inner part, like the flowers that the eye sees-are formed from the addition of internal compounds,"-the so - called. (11; B.37) *According to the type of syntactic communication (the type of subordination), the appearance of joint word combinations is as follows: a) two contiguous; a cute girl with a laugh, two anti-dependent classes struggling; b) two managerial contacts: a conversation on the topic with the leader; C) compatibility and manageable; a sadistic vision, my attitude to Labor; d) compatibility and cohesive: my hard labor, (11; B.37)*

3. The composition of complex word combinations also varies more than two independent meaningful words .tiradi A distinctive feature of complex word combinations is that in their composition, in addition to parts with a sign of independent authority, there will also be an element-lexical units with a sign of subordinate authority. For example: to be surprised as if talking with the parizodes in legends. (H.Shams). In the composition of the word combination, the part "to be surprised" is a part with a sign of absolute authority. This part is subject to all other lexical units contained in the syntactic device. The parizodes in the composition of this complex word combination, as they say, also have a sign of authority. But their sign of authority is not absolute, is of a compound character. Compare: be surprised as if talking with the parizodes of legends. In the composition of a complex word combination, it is possible to give examples of the participation of two to seven and even more dominant parts. The sounds of laughter coming out of the workshop-coming out of the workshop; like the sounds of laughter coming out of the workshop. Or two shredded juicy plums flowing from the middle of a plain planted cherry. (G'.Gulom).It is known that in the composition of the above complex word combination, combinations consisting of six dominant words are involved.. It can be shown on the basis of the table below:

Complex word combination "complexity" of the combination is not even in the plural of the amount of words in which they are contained. The interaction of structural elements and the methods of their connection are considered features that determine the complexity of such devices, - says professor A. Berdaliev. (11; B.38-40)

As the number of independent meaningful words in the composition of word combinations, in particular, parts with a sign of authority, increases, the complexity inherent in them again escalates. For example, two shredded juicy plums (G' G'.) flowing from the middle of a plain planted cherry, given above. let's guard by paying attention to the participation of seven dominant pieces in the combination. In this whole composition there are ten words with an independent meaning, consisting of several subordinate compound words, several dominant-word compound words and one absolute dominant. It is also said that the independent words that make up them have entered into a syntactic relationship between themselves with the help of six adjectives, a single-controlled connection. (11; B.39-40)

As a result, it is shown that the syntagmatic properties of complex word combinations are simpler and have a more complex appearance than the relative compound to the syntagmatic properties of compound sentences, therefore, it is necessary to study them separately and open unknown edges. (11; B.40)

Well, in the studies analyzed above, the classification of word combinations professor N.A. Baskakov noted, it is necessary to carry out on syntactic, morphological and synthetic-functional principles. In studies carried out so far, the main emphasis is on the classification of simple word combinations, with almost little attention paid to complex word combinations and their theoretical aspects. Therefore, it is worthwhile to classify complex vocabulary in the Uzbek literature, based on the semantic, syntactic and functional characteristics of complex vocabulary into complex vocabulary with nouns and verbs.

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TECHNOLOGY OF DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE FOLKLORE PERFORMERS THROUGH FOLKLORE SONGS SPECIFIC TO JIZZAX REGION

To‘rayeva Maftuna G‘ulomjonovna

Uzbekistan state art and culture institute
Folklore and ethnography department teacher

Abstract : This scientific in the article Jizzakh province to the territory typical folklore songs by means of future folklore performers professional competence develop technology scientific-theoretical and practical in terms of is illuminated . Local song examples (ritual , seasonal , labor , lyrical and executive traditions) study to the process step by step integration to do through in students vocal performance skill , style hearing , rhythmic - movement harmony , stage culture and ethnocultural thinking formation mechanisms working from the exit consists of . The article competency-based approach , ethnopedagogy and practical-executive methods in harmony offer " diagnostics - modeling - practical " "execution - reflection - evaluation " chain based on education technology described .

Keywords : folklore songs , upcoming folklore performer , professional competence , competency approach , ethnopedagogy

Today globalization and digital culture under the circumstances people oral creativity examples , particularly regional folklore songs execution both in practice and education new in the system to the tests face is coming . On the one hand , the public of culture fast spread , scene standards one diversification , "universal" repertoires increase as a result territorial style and execution of schools to oneself typical signs disappearance danger is increasing . The second from the side , higher in education future folklore performers preparation in the process local repertoire systematic to teach , its performance-poetic layers analysis to do and to the stage suitable in the interpretation to deliver according to methodical approaches every always enough at the level not technologically advanced .

Jizzakh province folklore in the environment ceremony and seasonal songs , work songs , lyric words , terms and executive traditions harmonious colors repertoire available . This repertoire future performer professional competence in formation natural " learning " "laboratory " function does : it not only voice opportunities right directs , perhaps methodological hearing , rhythmic - movement harmony , improvisational thinking , stage communication , text and melody attitude understanding , ethnocultural memory such as skills complex develops . Therefore territorial folklore the songs education " subject " to the process not as " , but as " technological as a resource input today especially is relevant .

Subject scientific and practical importance is that in the article offer attainable approach future folklore performers readiness based on the competency model assessment and to develop service In particular , " diagnostics – modeling – practical "execution - reflection - evaluation " chain through study process step by

step order is being performed , repertoire choice criteria clarified , training scenarios and indicators system (intonation) precision , methodical compatibility , stage culture , community with execution collaboration , improvisation elements) As a result , in the conditions of universities folklore education local to tradition relying on modern pedagogical tools with harmony opportunity expands , regional cultural inheritance storage and from generation to generation transmission to the process education system through stable contribution is added .

Folklore performance – national " living " culture " memory " of the people historical experience , worldview , tradition and aesthetic taste musical-poetic in the form embodied will come . Uzbek people folklore in the composition song genre separately place holds : ceremony and seasonal songs social life rhythm , work songs marriage style and values , lyrical words and spiritual experiences and spiritual the world represents . This in the sense folklore songs future performer professional in the formation not only repertoire source , maybe pedagogical-psychological impact to the power has educational and methodical tool as also appreciated .

Latest in years supreme in education art directions according to expert preparation in the process competency-based approach wide is being used . This approach from the performer only to sing or to the stage exit skill not , maybe methodological thinking , creative interpretation , communicative culture , community with performance , repertoire choice and analysis to do , staged image create such as integrative competencies demand However practice this shows that the future folklore performers in preparation territorial folklore materials often episodic in a separate way sample as) is studied ; it of education stages , targeted indicators and assessment criteria relied on at the " technology " level systematization issue enough at the level not illuminated .

Jizzakh province to the territory typical folklore songs this regarding big scientific and practical to the potential has . Jizzakh folklore in the environment melody pronunciation with harmony , I say naturalness , rhythmic of the movement stage culture with connection , community of execution active elements and local dialect and poetic of images lively application This is features future performer vocal performance qualification methodological accuracy with reinforcement , stage interpretation and interpretation skills enrichment , the most importantly , ethnocultural thinking in formation effective tool be takes .

Jizzakh province folklore songs based on future folklore performers professional competence to develop directed education technology justification and practical recommendations statement In the article following tasks marked : (1) regional the songs choice and didactic classification criteria determination ; (2) competence composition (vocal , instrumental) hearing , stage culture , rhythm-movement harmony , creative interpretation) indicators based on (3) “ diagnostics – modeling – practical "performance - reflection - evaluation " sequence based on training technology description ; (4) study in the process teacher – student tradition and modern pedagogical methods harmonization their ways show

Future folklore performer preparation in the process territorial folklore to the songs to rely on is only repertoire expansion not , maybe performance competence complex to develop service doer methodical is a direction .

Folklore song of the people aesthetic taste , historical memory , ritual-cultural experience and execution tradition " living " art that unites shape as education in the process many edged task does . Especially Jizzakh province to the territory typical song samples execution style , tone structure , text poetics and execution environment in terms of to oneself typical to be a student - performer vocal technician opportunities , methodological to hear ability and stage expression culture enriches .

Professional competence concept folklore performance in the context of following structural parts through manifestation will be : (1) vocal-performance competence (intonation , breathing , timbre) control , range , articulation); (2) methodological competence (territorial tone , pronunciation , performance style , dynamics and phrasing to tradition suitable (3) rhythmic movement and ensemble competence (team) with performance , traditional rhythm feeling , body plasticity to music harmony); (4) interpretative-creative competence (interpretation , improvisation , variation , poetic content opening); (5) stage-communicative competence (audience with dialogue , scene culture , psychological stability); (6) ethnocultural competence (ceremony context , tradition semantics , values system). So yes , regional the songs education process every one competence separately not a single system as development necessary .

Regional song samples performance competence " natural" in shaping study as "material " to value has . Because folklore song music in the and of the text organic unity , (b) execution environment (ritual , season , work) process , assembly) with integral connection , (c) execution in the process variation and improvisation elements , (d) collective execution tradition and travel methods sums up . So, the future performer professional formation for not "memorizing " the song , but " in context " " mastery " principle necessary : song when , how in the situation , how in tone and timbre pronunciation ; text how accent with interpretation to be done ; in execution how ornaments , pauses , rhythmic accents use of these all competence determinant are the criteria .

Regional folklore songs based on education technology in creation first important step – repertoire didactic to the goal suitable is a choice . Repertoire when choosing following criteria priority to be to the goal according to :

1. Genre and functional diversity : ritual (wedding , circumcision , cradle), seasonal (spring , harvest) , labor (harvest , livestock) , lyrical words , terms and executive samples in balance These competencies are selected different aspects wakes up : ceremony songs stage-communicative and contextual competence ; lyrical words vocal expression and interpretation ; labor songs rhythm - harmony of movement strengthens .
2. Complexity Level : study to the stage suitable accordingly simple range , repetitive to the rhythm has , clearly phrasing from songs starting from , then ornate , variant , wide range , dramatic requiring interpretation to samples He wished .
3. Style typicality : to the area typical pronunciation , tone turns , timbre requirements , travel methods clear noticeable " typical " patterns to the base is taken . Typical samples future in the performer methodological the norm shapes .
4. Educational potential : song text educational idea , value , socio-ethical content take walk ; in execution stage speech , diction , image create opportunity to give ; team with work skills to apply conditions create

5. Source reliability : song samples writing taken options , teacher performers interpretation , local performance to tradition compatibility is checked . In education random , " staged " sent " or territorial to style suitable not been options normative standard as not being given necessary .

Didactic classification and the songs training to the purpose according to grouping in mind For example : (a) intonation accuracy developer songs ; (b) breath and phrasing amplifier songs ; (c) rhythm-movement harmony developer songs ; (d) image and interpretation demand doer songs ; (e) ensemble / group performance for suitable songs . In this way repertoire " learned " not " list " , but targeted pedagogical tools to the system turns .

In the article offer being done technology study process step by step and to the result directed in a way organization to reach Technological approach at the center of " diagnostics - modeling - practical" "performance - reflection - evaluation " sequence This chain is folklore performer in preparation traditional " teacher" shows – disciple repeats the " model" denial does not , on the contrary , it modern didactics elements with enriches and the process controllable to the point brings .

Technology main principles the following :

- Contextual teaching principle : song his/her own ceremonial or social from duty cut off not allowed . Teaching in the process of the song come exit environment , pronunciation reason , traditional execution conditions , text semantics explained .
- Competency integration : every one training one of time in the room one how many develops competence (vocal , style , stage , ensemble) . For example , on " intonation " working with " diction " and " text" "from the accent" inseparable .
- Variability and creative interpretation : folklore The song " One " " right " look stiff There will be no more . The student different options compares , differences the reason analysis does , but methodically the norm without breaking creative interpretation to do learns .
- Step by step complicate : exercises simple from skills complicated execution to the tasks is redirected . Every one new stage previous stage indicators after strengthening is entered .
- Reflection and himself assessment : future performer his/her own strong and weak sides according to to receive , to perform mistakes reason with analysis to do , to fix strategy choice necessary . This and professional growth important is a condition .

Technology model within lesson process following from components is composed of : (1) motivational-contextual introduction ; (2) vocal-technical preparation ; (3) methodical listen and analysis ; (4) practical execution (individual and ensemble); (5) stage interpretation and action ; (6) reflection ; (7) criterion assessment and house task Diagnostics is not about " sorting " a student , but his/her there is opportunities identifying and individual development the way is to determine . In diagnostics the following checked : sound range and timbre feature ; intonation stability ; rhythm feeling ; diction and pronunciation ; stage at the exit psychological situation ; in the team work custom ; folklore text understanding level .

Diagnostics result based on student "competence" for "profile" is formed: for example, someone has voice opportunity strong, but methodical pronunciation slow; else rhythm good, but stage confidence enough Not. This profile next stages direction determines.

In modeling of the song execution model created: tone phrases divided, breath places are marked, accents are determined, the text semantic centers found, methodical ornaments (melismatic turns, stretches) normative in appearance. At this stage, the "listen – compare – conclude" mechanism is used. works. Student different execution options listening, "which element is regional?" to style "What element is typical?", "What element is typical?" "the result?" questions around analysis. Modeling as a result student the song conscious execution to reach approaches: it only by heart can't, maybe what for so to be said understands.

Practical execution technology central part divided, individual and ensemble exercises unites. In individual performance voice technique, diction, intonation, interpretation on is worked on; in an ensemble and each other to hear, the tone harmony, rhythm hold to stand, on stage joint action, movement with coordination skills develops. Practical execution "micro-skills" method in the process effective: for example, first 2–3 phrases, then a paragraph, then complete song; first simple tone, then decorated elements; first sitting down execution, then with stage action performance. Also, the student's Record the performance with audio/video to take practice reflection for very useful. It will be.

Reflection – performance analysis to make a mistake see and correction strategy working exit is the stage. Here student following criteria based on own performance evaluates: intonation (purity) and stability, breathing (correct distribution), diction (text clarity), stylistic compatibility (territorial of the tone perception), stage expression (image, communication), ensemble harmony. In reflection teacher's role – "error" "You did it" not "error" what because of face "gave?" to the question. For example, intonation escape of breath wrong distribution or in pronunciation from stress to be possible. Reason if found, fix. The exercise is also clear. It will be.

Evaluation competency-based indicators through done. The traditional "like - dislike" approach instead of criterion assessment used: (a) intonation accuracy; (b) rhythmic stability; (c) text clarity; (d) methodological compatibility; (e) stage culture; (f) ensemble collaboration; (g) creative interpretation. Each indicator 3 levels (beginner - intermediate - advanced) simplified assessment the system is also sufficient to be possible. Importantly, evaluation student's growth show me and next training purpose by designating let him give.

Regional folklore the songs in teaching effective training usually in the chain of "context - analysis - performance - interpretation - scene" relies on. Below technology practical aspect illuminating methods is quoted:

Exercise at first of the song come exit atmosphere, ceremonial place, pronunciation purpose short story.

To students one of the song two or three kind execution from the option fragments They are listening to the differences . record comes : tempo, stress , length , ornamentation , pronunciation , pause . Then " which one territorial to style " Is it close ?" discussion This method is methodological to hear and analytical thinking strengthens .

Song to phrases is divided into . In each phrase separately habit exercise is done : one in a phrase breath , in the second diction , in the third decoration . So phrases is connected . As a result song " from the beginning " " until the end " text not , maybe controllable execution structure as is being adapted .

Student song in the text image and determines mood (joy , health , wish , irony , humor) and in performance this tries to express . Teacher questions gives : "In this paragraph to whom appeal " Is there ?", " Main" word Which one ?", " Urg' u where to be "Is this method necessary ?" stage-communicative competence increases .

Folklore performance often collective happened because of ensemble exercises mandatory : one group leader the melody , another group the journey , again one rhythmic applause or action elements This method does solidarity , each other hearing , stage harmony strengthens .

This methods Uzbekistan state art and culture institute such as education in institutions practical exercises competency-based basically planning and take on the way application for Most importantly , the methods follow the " teacher - student " tradition . modern didactics with awakens : teacher sample shows , disciple repeats , but this repeat " conscious " analysis " and " criteria with " growth " together It's going to happen . In general in the article working issued technology Uzbekistan state art and culture institute and other art in the direction of In universities future folklore performers preparation process practical in terms of improvement , education content territorial tradition with enrichment and folklore legacy stable transmission mechanisms to strengthen service does . Therefore this approach study plans , practical training system , repertoire banks and assessment criteria step by step current to grow future folklore performers professional readiness quality in increasing important factor to be service does .

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MIEN HAZRAT MADRASAH
Sodikov Khurshidbek Solizhon ugli
2nd Year Student of KSPI

Abstract

This article highlights an educated and statesman named Miona Fazilova, as well as the history of the construction of the Mien Hazrat madrasah in the city of Kokand.

Keywords: Kokand, The Palace of Khudoyorkhan, Sakhibzada Khazrat, Mukhammad Aminkhodja Mukumi, Abdusamadboy, Furkat, Askarali Khamraliev Charkhi, Ubaydulla Salikh ugli Zavkiy, Iskandarkhodja, H.N. Bobobekov.

Introduction

The city of Kokand is one of the historical cities of Uzbekistan, which managed to preserve its historical appearance, where such ancient architectural monuments as the Khudayarkhan Palace, the Zhami Mosque, Norbutabiya, the Mien Hazrat Madrasah, Kamol Kazy, the mausoleum of Dahmai Shokhon and others are located.

According to the importance and number of historical sites, the city of Kokand occupies the most important place among other cities of Uzbekistan. According to H.N. Bobobekov, in the XIX century there were 348 mosques in Kokand (among them 18 zhami), about 40 madrasahs, 26 sanctuaries, more than a hundred khanaks, and many central and dozens of specialized bazaars, about thirty caravanserais [1.218-224]. It should be emphasized that a lot of the architectural diversity of Kokand included not only national samples, but also dozens of objects made in the European style.

Discussion

One of the most interesting places in the Ferghana Valley, more precisely in the city of Kokand, is the Mien Hazrat Madrasah, which was built in 1861. The madrasah was built at the request of an outstanding scientist and statesman named Min File Ahad, who received the respectful name Sahibzoda Hazrat among the people. It is known that he moved to Kokand from Peshawar in 1832 at the special invitation of the ruler Madali Khan, who considered him his spiritual teacher. The famous poet, satirist and writer Muhammad Amin Khoja Mukimi also lived and worked in the madrasah [2.74-75].

Abdusamadboy, a local merchant, played an important role in inviting him to Kokand. Mien Ahad, who has an unsurpassed intellect and deep religious knowledge, is gaining great authority. He will even be made an adviser to the khan. Mien Ahad from a historically wealthy family inherited a large amount of property from Pakistan and

used it to build a madrasah in Kokand. The madrasah building has been preserved to this day.

The madrasah building consists of a complex with three courtyards. Two courtyards are connected by an east-west axis, and the third one adjoins them from the south.

The domed entrance to the madrasah is located on the western side of the southern courtyard with soft carved gates. These wooden carved gates were built by Kokand master Iskandar Khoja. There are rooms (32x26) around the southern courtyard, and the mosque has many columns on the south side. The story is rectangular, with a flat roof. There is also a signora on the southeast side of this courtyard. But it has

been preserved in a severely damaged condition [3].

The eastern courtyard (35x20) and the western courtyard (23x11) are also surrounded by rooms. There was a porch to the east of the madrasah, but today it has not been preserved. There is a classroom on the west side. The walls are made of baked brick and plastered with plaster [1.222-223].

The roofs of the madrasah are shallow. It is covered with domes and beams. The exterior is made of baked brick, and the interior is plastered with a gypsum mixture. It is believed that its division into such a system of courtyards was due to the grouping of subjects taught.

According to historical sources, initially there were about 60 rooms in the madrasah. However, today only the southern courtyard is perfectly preserved, in which only 24 rooms remain. In addition to religious studies, secular sciences are taught in the madrasah. For example, literature, mathematics, astronomy, history, and so on. Outstanding poets and scientists of the Kokand Khanate studied at the madrasah. These are Muhammad Amin khoja Mukimi, Furkat, Askarali Hamraliev Charkhi, Ubaidullah Salih oglu Applications and others. The second room on the right was occupied by the sensitive poet Mukimi. On the left lived Charkhi, and in the next room lived and studied Applications.

There is no architect of the building in the sources, only the master who made the magnificent carved gates, that is, Iskandar Khoja, is mentioned. The new madrasah was built in the old residential quarter (mahalla) not by demolishing houses, but by building vacant lots. Therefore, the object received a bizarre shape and seemed to consist of three courtyards. This feature was successfully beaten functionally: each of them was designed for different levels of training: adno (primary), avsat (secondary)

and alo (higher). In the 30s of the twentieth century, a weaving artel was opened in the madrasah, and later a factory.

In 1939, on the initiative of Charkhi and Ruzimukhammad Dostmatov (Mukimi's nephew), the Mukimi House-Museum was established at the madrasa. In accordance with the decision of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on preparations for the celebration of the anniversary of the city of Kokand, the Mien Hazrat madrasah was included in the repair work program for 2010-2011, among other facilities. In recent years, more than 250 architectural monuments have been surveyed on the territory of the Fergana Valley of Uzbekistan. These are civil and memorial-religious buildings, including residential buildings, a palace, baths, mosques, minarets, madrassas and mausoleums. Some have already been restored, others need restoration work, and others, unfortunately, are completely lost.

Conclusion

On June 24, 2021, it was decided to declare Kokand the first tourist capital at the VI meeting of the Ministers of Tourism of the Cooperation Council of Turkic-speaking States [4]. At the end of the article, I would like to say that we, the people of independent Uzbekistan, should cherish and respect the cultural heritage, architectural monuments created and carefully preserved by our ancestors for many centuries. This is the responsibility of each of us!

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CHARACTERISTICS OF ENGLISH TEACHING METHODS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Shavkatjonova Maftuna Furkatovna,

Teacher of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract

This article explores the unknown aspects of the topic being studied in a way that encourages students to think more and easily memorize new words and terms in the process of teaching English in non-philological educational institutions and present issues that will be understandable and interesting for students to express their new knowledge.

Keywords: non-philological educational institutions, memory-strengthening exercises, “chain drill”, broken telephone”, Speaker with Translator”.

Introduction

One of the current issues is to educate the younger generation in the spirit of love and devotion to the motherland, national pride, high morals and spirituality, pride in our ancient and rich heritage, national and universal values through the teaching of foreign languages. Radical reforms in the world education system raise the problem of creating the necessary conditions for students to learn foreign languages perfectly, to express themselves in all areas with knowledge of a foreign language, to develop their oral and written speech in a foreign language. Organizations such as UNESCO, UNICEF, the European University Association, the European Network for Higher Education Quality are involved in the development of students' thinking in a foreign language, the ability to speak fluently, the formation of intellectual activity, the assessment of their readiness. is being used. The development of these issues in general trends plays an important role in the formation of modern and foreign language skills in the younger generation and serves to increase the creative abilities of students in connection with the problems of modern education.

In the reform of the education system of the Republic, the coordination of educational programs based on foreign experience in accordance with international standards has become the basis for improving the system of higher pedagogical education. In the context of Uzbekistan, a radical reform of the quality of education based on foreign experience, taking into account our national mentality and traditions, is a requirement of the times. In this regard, the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 states: To stimulate research and innovation, to create effective mechanisms for the implementation of scientific and innovative achievements, to improve the quality of training, to create the necessary conditions for the training of qualified specialists in accordance with

international standards, each higher education institution to establish close cooperation with educational institutions and develop students' creative abilities, effective use of interactive methods in working with young audiences, to provide them with quality education in a foreign language, to raise the level of higher education to an exemplary level and Improvements have been identified as key objectives [1].

Therefore, in order to form the ability to read the original literature on the specialty, to participate in oral communication in a foreign language in the process of production of future personnel in the higher education system of the republic and finding the information necessary for scientific purposes classes are being held.

Every citizen of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan must be able to read the original literature in a foreign language, understand the text and use it in their profession. He should also be able to communicate freely in a foreign language with his interlocutor on a given topic. Indeed, the study of foreign languages is a requirement of today's globalized world.

Thanks to independence, special attention is paid to the teaching of foreign languages in our country. Thousands of foreign language teachers have been trained, all conditions have been created for staff to improve their skills in our country and abroad, multimedia textbooks in English, German and French, electronic resources for learning English have been prepared. The organization of language rooms is a clear proof of this. The main goal is to improve the education of the younger generation in foreign languages and the training of specialists who are fluent in these languages, to create conditions for young people to use the achievements of world civilization and world information resources, international cooperation and dialogue. The famous German scientist Y.V. As von Goethe said, "He who does not know a foreign language does not know his own language." For this reason, it is very important not only for foreign language specialists, but also for all future professionals studying in non-language universities to be able to learn foreign languages and communicate freely. There is a proverb among our people: "He who knows the language knows". Indeed, a person who knows a foreign language will have many opportunities and advantages. One of the main requirements for staff today is a perfect knowledge of foreign languages [3].

In order to form the ability to read the original literature on the specialty, to participate in oral communication in a foreign language in the process of training future personnel in the higher education system of the Republic and finding the information necessary for scientific purposes, English lessons wishing. An expert in his or her field should be able to read original English-language literature, understand the text, and apply it in his or her profession. In addition, he should be able to communicate freely in a foreign language with his interlocutor on a given topic [4].

In non-language higher education institutions, the teaching of English through interactive methods has a positive effect, thereby further developing students'

thinking, learning and imparting information in English, new knowledge of English, scientific research in their field. allows you to track changes and stay informed of news, and this expands students 'worldview. It is interesting and useful for students to work on relevant materials in their profession. To do this, the student must first know the meaning, pronunciation and use of new words or terms in the text. We use a variety of interactive methods. For example, the chain drill method. Students pronounce an audio of a new word or term and say it with a translation of a word they have learned well, and the next student repeats the word without translation and adds another word they have learned. puts. Thus, the game continues until the last student's word, where the word order can help the student repeating the words only in Uzbek or Russian, otherwise he will leave the game. This game helps the student to memorize new words more easily and with interest [5].

The second method is to divide the group into 2 or 3 small groups and stand in a row and reinforce the words through a "broken telephone" game. In this case, the student standing first composes a sentence using new words and phrases and tells it to the ear of the student standing behind him, and he tells it to the next student, and so the game continues. And the game continues until you reach the last student. The main task of the game is to work with the team and to feel the responsibility to fully understand and convey the opinion of each student. They learn a lot in the process of understanding and delivering. The first group to submit an error-free opinion is the winner. Now it's much easier to work with groups that have mastered the words. Students listen to the text over audio and observe the written form. The second time the audio is played, the teacher distributes the new words in the same text in the omitted form. The student has to listen to it for a while and fill it in no matter what. The result of this practical work is checked with all groups of students and worked on errors. The text is now divided into 2 or 3 parts and distributed to groups. Depending on the group's ability, time is set and they are given a task in the form of a game "Speaker with Translator", in which each student works as an interpreter and speaker does. In this way it is processed one by one. The rest of the groups follow up on their mistakes and shortcomings and write feedback on their work and talk in English about what they have learned through their speech and translation. The rest of the groups work the same way. The price is set by the students themselves. In this hands-on activity, each student strives for the quality of their group work [6].

These methods, especially in non-philological educational institutions, help to learn words and terms quickly and easily, to express independent opinions, to explain to peers, to improve the teaching skills of students of the same level and to actively participate in elective classes. does. An individual comment given by the teacher at the end of the lesson will motivate the students. The task of the groups is to find additional information about the given text or processed texts and to prepare various presentations. This allows students to search for more information related to the

topic, to exchange ideas and to connect their ideas based on the presentations, to use grammar correctly, provides the ability to work independently from dictionaries. Apparently, the student is not bored or overworked, but participates with a desire to learn and a desire to improve their knowledge.

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FORMING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AMONG YOUTH AS ONE OF THE COMPONENTS OF SPIRITUAL AND SOCIAL WELL-BEING

Rakhimov Mavlon Baimurodavich
Lecturer, National Institute of Arts and
Design. K. Behzoda, Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan

Annotation

Ensuring a healthy lifestyle is an important task of each state. In the process of forming a healthy lifestyle, physical education and physical culture is an important means of social and biomedical orientations of the young generation. In the process of physical education and physical culture of young people, comprehensive preparation is received for life and professional activities.

Keywords: healthy lifestyle, youth, physical education, physical culture, comprehensive training.

Introduction

Healthy youth, physically strong, is the main asset of any state. It is worth paying attention to a number of important state acts: "The Law on Physical Culture and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures for the Further Development of Physical Culture and Mass Sports", "On the Fundamentals of the State Youth Policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan", "On protection of the health of citizens".

Let us dwell on one of the significant factors in the formation of healthy lifestyle habits - Physical activity, i.e. motor. Its specific feature is that it is directly and directly aimed at man's mastery of his own physical nature. Physical activity underlies the phenomenon - physical culture. The historical aspects of the emergence of physical culture are still debatable. Some scientists associate them with the form of leisure activities, others with the development of labor activity and the social need for effective means and methods of forming the necessary physical and spiritual qualities in the younger generation; the third - with the desire of people to resolve personal conflicts in a bloodless way. Today, physical culture is an integral part of modern civilization.

The formation of a healthy lifestyle among young people is a complex systemic process that covers many components of the lifestyle of modern society and includes the main areas and areas of life of young people. The focus of young people on maintaining a healthy lifestyle depends on many conditions. These are both socio-economic and objective social conditions that make it possible to lead and implement a healthy lifestyle in the main areas of human life and activity.

The relevance of the problem of forming a healthy lifestyle among the youth is due to the critical state of the physical and spiritual development of the younger generation.

The causes of health disorders are both environmental factors and risk factors that have a behavioral basis. Namely, smoking, drinking alcohol, "nasvay", toxic and narcotic substances, which leads to a lack of interest in regular physical education, non-compliance with the rules of personal hygiene. The health status of the population, i.e. children and youth is the most important indicator of the well-being of society and the state. Therefore, strengthening the health of the population, a significant reduction in the level of socially significant diseases, creating conditions and shaping motivation for a healthy lifestyle is one of the priority tasks of the state. Great attention to the problem of forming a healthy lifestyle deserves student youth, which is the main source of replenishment of the labor resources of our society. To help students understand high demands on themselves, the ability to lead a healthy lifestyle, the vital need to work, help them understand that smoking, substance abuse, drug addiction, alcoholism and beer alcoholism are a big problem and you need to take care of your health.

The processes taking place in modern society have exacerbated the problems of maintaining and developing human health and the formation of a healthy lifestyle. The level of health determines all human life in a wide range of social life, on the other hand, it is considered as the most important condition for the reproduction and quality of the labor force and human potential in general. The main aspects of a healthy lifestyle of young people are the mode of work and rest, physical activity, personal hygiene, rejection of bad habits, rational nutrition, environmentally competent behavior, preventive thinking.

Methodological recommendations are required on the formation of a healthy lifestyle among young people in order to form public opinion about the need to maintain a healthy lifestyle and the need for systematic physical education and sports among young people.

It is worth mentioning beer and low-alcohol drinks, which are beginning to be popular with young people, and sometimes backed up by advertising. Adolescence is the most dangerous age in terms of addiction to harmful health phenomena.

To ensure the effectiveness of the programs on a healthy lifestyle, it is not enough just to organize one-day sports events. All levels working with the population and youth are needed, starting from school and ending with the formation of a system of information, scientific and methodological support for activities aimed at promoting a healthy lifestyle among young people, involving them in physical education and sports.

The solution to this problem is possible with a one-time, full-scale work in the regions with young people through the organization of the promotion of a healthy lifestyle. Development and expansion of available sections, holding many regular sports events. The work of specialists with youth, i.e. doctors, psychologists and teachers. It is recommended to promote work on the prevention of cigarette smoking and the "nasvay" of alcoholism, drug addiction, substance abuse. Formation of motivation for the younger generation to lead a healthy lifestyle.

To host events:

a) Aimed at reducing the prevalence of prevention of risk factors among young people (tobacco, nasvay, alcoholism);

b) Aimed at optimizing the regulation of risk factors (nutrition of the population, in particular schoolchildren).

Promoting a healthy lifestyle is the purposeful dissemination of information through mass sources with the aim of influencing public opinion and generating interest among various population groups in physical education and sports and maintaining a healthy lifestyle.

Educational work among the population, including children, adolescents and youth. Formation of an active public opinion in relation to counteracting and combating asocial phenomena and promoting a healthy lifestyle among young people: organizing work with the media, organizing social advertising, conducting explanatory work among the population, organizing preventive assistance to adolescents and young people, forming anti-drug views and beliefs. Young people should prioritize the formation of fashion for a healthy lifestyle.

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